

**“STUDY OF PREVALENCE OF MYOPIA IN SCHOOL
GOING CHILDREN IN BIJAPUR CITY.”**

By

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Anterior Chamber
BP	Blood pressure
C/D	Cup disc
CMA	Compound myopic astigmatism
D	Dioptre
EOG	Electrooculogram
ERG	Electroretinography
Fig.	Figure
Govt.	Government
H/O	History of
i.e.	That is
ICR	Intracorneal ring
IOL	Intraocular lens
IOP	Intraocular pressure
LASIK	Laser in - situ keratomileusis
LE	Left eye
mm	Millimeter
nm	Nanometer
PH	Pin hole
PM	Pathological myopia
PR	Pulse rate
PRK	Photorefractive Keratectomy
PVD	Posterior vitreous detachment

RE	Right eye
RK	Radial Keratotomy
RPE	Retinal prignent epithelium
RR	Respiratory rate
Rs.	Rupees
SM	Simple myopia
SMA	Simple myopic astigmatism
SRNV	Subretinal neovascularisation
Tempt	Temperarture
UM	Unilateral myopia
VA	Visual acuity
χ^2	Chi-square
Yrs	Years
SPK	superficial punctuate keratitis
VKC	vernal keratoconjunctivitis
B	Blepharitis
CX	conjunctival xerosis
BS	bitot's spot

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND

Refractive error is being the most common cause of visual impairment, in that myopia is the commonest cause. Uncorrected myopia is major public eye health problem in school- going children in India. Refractive Error, and particularly myopia, places a substantial burden on the individual and on society. Therefore the magnitude of the problem needs a systematic assessment.

AIMS:

This study evaluates the prevalence of myopia in school going children in Bijapur city.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a cross sectional and time bound study in which simple random sampling among school going children between 7-15 years of age were chosen for the study. Among the schools in Bijapur city, 6 schools were randomly selected for the study for a period of 1 year from October 2012 to March 2014. A detailed history regarding the personnel details, annual income of family, any presenting complaints, past history of wearing glasses was taken. The examination included thorough ocular torch light examination with special concentration to the visual axis by performing Hirschberg's test. A visual acuity cut off of 6/9 was taken. The children with visual defects underwent an objective cycloplegic retinoscopy followed by subjective correction.

RESULTS

A total of 1,374 students were participated in study. The prevalence of myopia was found in 8.2% students. Increasing age was associated with the increased risk of having myopia. Girl students were more likely to have myopia than boys. The

prevalence of myopia among girls was more than that of boys 9.5% and 7.0% respectively. Students from high socio-economic status were having higher prevalence of myopia than their counterparts from low socio-economic counterparts. More time spent on near work have been reported to increase the risk of myopia.

CONCLUSION

Vision screening of school children in developing countries could be useful in detecting correctable causes of decreased vision, especially refractive errors, and in minimizing long term permanent visual disability.

Keywords: Myopia,Prevalence,Scio-economic status.

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INTRODUCTION

Eyes are windows of learning and visual appreciation of objects that contribute to learning in any individual's life. Visual disability in childhood can be minimized or can even be prevented, if the cause is detected earlier and treated before they become irreversible.

Childhood blindness is one of the priorities in Vision 2020: the right to sight.¹ It is estimated that there are 1.4 million blind children in the world, two thirds of whom live in the developing countries,² and that the causes of blindness in children vary according to region and socioeconomic development.^{2,3} Many of the causes of blindness in children are either preventable or treatable.

Blindness due to natural refractive error can hinder education, personality development, and career opportunities, in addition to causing an economic burden to society.

There are 12.8 million children in the age group of 5–15 years who are visually impaired from uncorrected or inadequately corrected refractive errors, a global prevalence of 0.96%, with the highest prevalence reported in urban and highly developed urban areas in south-east Asia.⁴ The incidence of blindness in children is very difficult to ascertain, requiring either very large longitudinal studies, accurate registers of the blind, or reliable active surveillance systems.⁵ Refractive errors are common in children and are the commonest cause of visual impairment around the world and the second leading cause of treatable blindness.

According to one regional study, In India the prevalence of childhood blindness was 0.17%. Treatable refractive error caused 33.3% of the blindness, followed by 16.6% due to preventable causes (8.3% each due to vitamin A deficiency

and amblyopia after cataract surgery). The major causes of blindness included congenital eye anomalies (16.7%) and retinal degeneration (16.7%).⁶

Since in developed countries the majority of children attend schools or preschools, it is relatively easier to reach them by vision screening programs. However, in developing countries many children do not attend school, and they are therefore missed by vision screening programs conducted in schools.

For the age group 5–15 years, the prevalence of visual impairment from uncorrected refractive errors in some regions appears to be higher in urban areas than in rural areas, despite access to services. This may be due to a high incidence of myopia in these populations: it is suggested that there may be a direct cause–effect relation between increased access to education and myopia, but other secular changes could be contributing factors.⁴

Uncorrected myopia is major public eye health problem in school- going children in India. Refractive Error, and particularly myopia, places a substantial burden on the individual and on society.⁷

School myopia occurs at approximately 7-17 years of age and stabilizes by the late teens or early twenties. Over the past few decades, there has been an increase in the prevalence of myopia in some populations, leading to growing concern among the public and the scientific community. There is no well established or universally accepted treatment for the prevention of myopia onset or progression.⁸

The importance of early detection and treatment of visual impairment in children in India is obvious, because 30 % of these blind children lose their sight before 20 years of age.⁹ Poor vision in childhood affects performance in school or at work and has a negative influence on the future life of the child.¹⁰

Ninety seven percent of all visual disabilities are preventable or treatable. Refractive error is the commonest type of ocular morbidity and myopia is the commonest type of refractive error as opposed to hypermetropia.¹¹

The care of a child's sight should commence at a very early phase of life at the nursery school level as it can bring out visual defects of which neither the patient nor its parents may be aware. The value of school clinics where the eyes of every school going child can be examined periodically, any refractive errors corrected early and any required guidance given properly.

As myopia is the most prevalent in school going children (7 – 15 years of age), the visual morbidity can be reduced by screening programs in school. Hence, these screening programs with treatment should be promoted in all schools.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To study prevalence of myopia in school going children in Bijapur city.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

History

Aristotle (384-322 BC) was the first to describe short sight while it was only Galen (130-200AD) who attempted to put the problem of myopia within the physiological concepts of his days, the theory of humours. The optics of myopia was first elucidated by Johannes Kepler (1604) in his initial clarification of ophthalmic dioptrics when he correctly assumed that the incident light was brought to focus in front of retina. Von-Graefe (1954) was the first to correlate the ophthalmoscopic and degenerative changes of pathological myopia.¹² Hirschberg (1982) attributed the first discussion of myopia and presbyopia to Aristotle. The relevant discussions were entitled in Aristotle's book 'Problemata' and similar to this was Plato's book which constituted the oldest citations explaining the concept of myopia.¹³

Johannes Kepler (1571-1630) an astronomer and physicist had great impact on understanding of eye and its functions. He explained that convergence of light anterior to the retina is cause of myopia.¹³

Epidemiology

Prevalence

A. Global

The prevalence of myopia within sampled population often varies with age, country, sex, race, ethnicity, occupation, environment, and other factors. Variability in testing and data collection methods makes comparisons of prevalence and progression difficult.¹⁴

The prevalence of myopia varies by the country, age and by ethnic group it is a major cause of visual impairment in both the developed and the developing world.¹⁵

The prevalence of myopia has been reported to be as high as 70-90% in some Asian population with Taiwan reporting a myopic prevalence of 84% among 16-18 years old high school students.^{16,17} In Europe and America, its prevalence varies between 30–40%, while in Africa 10–20% of the population is affected.¹⁸ Myopia affects 25% of the population in United States.¹⁹

B. Asia

In some parts of Asia, myopia is very common. Singapore is believed to have the highest prevalence of myopia in the world; up to 80% of people there have myopia, but the accurate figure is unknown.²⁰ China's myopia rate is 31% : 400 million of its 1.3 billion people are myopic. The prevalence of myopia in high school in China is 77.3%, and in college is more than 80%.²¹ In some areas, such as China and Malaysia, up to 41% of the adult population is myopic to 1.00 D,²² and up to 80% to 0.5 D.²³

However, some research suggests the prevalence of myopia in India in the general population is only 6.9%.²⁴

Kalikivayi V et al., in 1997 studied 4,029 children between 3-18 years in Hyderabad city, India, prevalence of myopia to be 8.6% and was significantly higher in children 10 yrs of age ($p < 0.001$), supporting vision screening of school children in developing countries could be useful in detecting correctable causes of decreased vision in minimizing long term permanent visual disability. The most important cause of uncorrectable visual loss in this study was found to be amblyopia, mostly caused by refractive errors.²⁵

Murthy GV et al., in 2002 assessed the prevalence of refractive error and related visual impairment in school going children 5-15 years of age, in an urban population in New Delhi and reported a prevalence of 7.4% of myopia.²⁶

Fan DS et al., in 2004, screened 7,560 Chinese children in Hong Kong of mean age 9.33 yrs range between 5-16 yrs, has found myopia the most common refractive error, and was found in $36.7\% \pm 2.87\%$ of children, prevalence of myopia correlated positively with older age. Children aged 11 yrs were almost 15 times more likely to have myopia than were children younger than 7 yrs. Increasing age was correlated with increased incidence of myopia with highest risk in children of age 11 yrs.²⁷

Uzma et al, in 2009 conducted study in Hyderabad on school-aged children in urban and rural population showed provision of health education, periodic visual screening programs and primary eye care by trained health care personnel in elementary schools will help to detect early diagnosis of Myopia and common ocular diseases in school children.²⁸

Ghosh S et al, in 2012 conducted study in Kolkata on 2570 children of 10 primary schools. The age range was 6 – 14 years; refractive error was seen in 14.7%. Myopia was present in 307 (11.9%) visual acuity of less than 6/12 in better eye was present in 109 (4.2%) and 5 (0.2%) children pre and post-correction, respectively.²⁹

MYOPIA

The word myopia is derived from Greek language by Galen. In Greek - from the words myein means to close and ops means the eye (Borish 1970).

The word myopia describes the ancient observation that affected individuals habitually approximated their eyelids to form a stenopaic slit to improve the image quality. Myopia is also known as near sight because myopia persons have good uncorrected visual acuity at near within an arm's length.

Definition:

Myopia or short sight is that form of refractive error wherein parallel rays of light come to a focus in front of the sentient layer of the retina when the eye is at rest.

The first satisfactory definition of the condition was stated by Kepler in 1611, and Plempius (1632) first examined the myopic eye anatomically and attributed the condition to a lengthening of its posterior part. Donders (1866) established its pathological basis and detailed its clinical manifestations.³⁰

Myopia is an increasingly important global public eye health problem. In the past two decades, the prevalence among young adolescents has increased from 5-10% to 10-25% in industrialized societies in Europe and North America, and by over 25% to 60-80% in East Asia.³¹

Eye as an optical system:

To understand the behaviors of rays onto the retina and the mechanism of formation of an image on the retina, it is necessary to understand the various refractive elements in their path. Human eye has the following refractive structures within it.³²

- Anterior surface of cornea
- Posterior surface of cornea
- Aqueous humour
- Anterior surface of lens
- Substance of lens.
- Posterior surface of lens
- Vitreous humour.

All these structures are separated by an accurate distance from the anterior surface of the cornea. They also have different refractive indices with respect to each

other. The position and refractive index determine the behavior of light rays reaching the retina to form an image on it.

The light entering the eye is refracted markedly at the anterior corneal surface for two reasons. First of its curvature, the central spherical part having a radius of curvature usually a little less than 8 mm and secondly because of the highly significant difference in refractive indices of cornea and air that is $1.37 - 1 = 0.37$.

The light then undergoes little further refraction until it reaches the lens, at both surfaces of which it is again refracted. Refraction by the eye is therefore effectively takes place at two structures, the anterior corneal surface and the lens.

Refraction takes place to a significant degree only at three out of the four surfaces, and we ignore the refraction at the posterior surface of the cornea as its refractive index is practically same as that of aqueous humour. Furthermore the refractive indices of aqueous and vitreous are similar.

It follows that the major part of the ocular refraction takes place at the anterior surface of cornea. The optical power of which (40-45D) is over twice that of the lens (20D).

The light then undergoes little refraction till it reaches the lens where it is again refracted. The refractive indices differ between aqueous and lens but their difference is not more than the difference between cornea and air. Therefore the major portion of the refraction takes place at the anterior surface of the cornea its optical power is twice that of the lens.³³

There are some special features of refraction caused by the lens. The lens is made of several layers. The central nuclear layer has a index of refraction which is more than that of the peripheral layers. This will cause a progressive increase in optical density which will greatly increase its converging power and it will become a

greater powered lens. The greater refractive strength of the nucleus of the lens has a biological importance that is other than the ability to converge the rays of light on the retina it also helps in decreasing the optical errors of spherical and chromatic aberrations; it reduces the scattering of the light inside the eyeball. Since the power of varying the refraction depends on the refractivity of lens the structure of the lens helps in doubling the normal range.³⁴

At birth, the eyeball is relatively short having +2 to +3 Dioptre hypermetropia. This is gradually reduced until by the age of 5-7 yrs the eye is emmetropic and remains so till the age of about 50 years. After 50 yrs, there is a tendency to develop hypemetropia again which gradually increases until at the extreme of life and by 80 years, the eye has the same +2 to +3 Dioptre with which it started.³⁵

OPTICS OF MYOPIA

The dioptric power of a myopic eye is too powerful for its axial length or the eye is too long for its dioptric power, so that parallel rays of light come to a focus in front of the retina (Fig. 1A). And hence image of distant object on the retina is made up of the circles of diffusion formed by the divergent beam.

Far point (punctum remotum) in myopic eye is a finite point in front of the eye and higher the myopia shorter the distance therefore, a near object situated at the far point is focused without an effort of accommodation (Fig. 1B).

Fig. 1: Optics of myopia.

- a) Parallel rays are focused in front of retina;
- b) Divergent rays from an object at the far point of the eye are focused at the retina.

Nodal point in a myopic eye is farther away from the retina. Therefore, the image formed will be appreciably larger than it would be in the emmetropic eye. With correcting spectacles, however, the opposite holds good and the image appears smaller and brighter (Fig. 2 A & B). To some small extent, this compensates for the poor visual acuity.

Angle Kappa of the eye may be negative resulting in an apparent convergent squint.³⁵

Fig. 2: Image formed in an uncorrected myopia is larger than that formed by an emmetropic eye (A) and spectacle corrected myopia (B)

The visual acuity in myopia:

Visual acuity beyond the far point is seriously affected in uncorrected myopia, being reduced by about the same ratio as occurs in absolute hypermetropia (Eggers 1945).¹² It is impossible to predict accurately in any individual case what the uncorrected vision and refractive error in Dioptre should be, but it has been found that the visual acuity and the error, in general, are closely correlated.

Table 1: Visual acuity and myopia.

Myopia in D	-0.5	-1.0	-1.5	-2.0	-3.0	-4.0	-5.0	-6.0
VA	20/25	20/65	20/110	20/165	20/285	20/420	20/565	20/675

Accommodation in myopia:

Accommodation in myopia is not developed normally; since they need not accommodate to see the near objects clearly. This is of little value to the myope, but rather increases his difficulties. He has no means of reducing his myopia or increasing his vision apart from screwing up his lids in an attempt to attain the advantage of a stenopaic aperture.¹² At the same time, in the higher degrees of defect, it may not be without accommodative difficulties. In these cases range of accommodation is small.

It is because of the dissociation between accommodation and convergence, a considerable number of uncorrected myopic children develops strabismus. For this reason they may suffer from convergence insufficiency, exophoria, and early presbyopia as they grow. In contrast to esophoria in hypermetropia. Thus among 790 myopic children, Thomson (1919) found 65 squinters, of whom 27 diverged and 38 converged.

Thus the uncorrected nonaccommodating myopic eye has some point at a finite distance, beyond which objects will not be seen clearly. At this far point, an

object will be in clear focus, but with increasing distance beyond it, the image becomes progressively more indistinct. This far point is also defined as the focal point of the eye. The degree of myopia in Dioptres (D) is found by determining the reciprocal of the far point of the eye. Therefore, $P=1/f$

Where P is the power of the refractive error in Dioptres, and f is the distance of the far point or focal point of the eye in meters from the eye. If the far point of an eye is at 33.3cm then the eye is $1/0.333\text{m}=3\text{D}$ myopic.³⁶

Aetiology and Risk factors of Myopia:

1. **Age:** Myopia is common in premature infant, not so common in newborn infant, and rare by age 6 months. Premature and low birth weight infants have higher risk of developing myopia later in life, there is a sharp rise in incidence of myopia from ages 5-20 yrs and then gradually there is a decline in the incidence throughout middle and advancing age. The refraction of the infant eye averages +2.00 to +3.0 D. The prevalence of myopia is greatest in adolescence, reaching approximately 25% and reflecting the tendency of hyperopia to decrease and myopia to increase.
2. **Race:** There is difference in the prevalence of myopia among racial and ethnic groups. The highest prevalence of myopia is among oriental races, reaching 50-70 % of Chinese and 30% of Japanese. Eskimos, Native Americans, and black Africans have low prevalence of myopia. In Asia, the prevalence of myopia is highest in urban Chinese populations such as Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore and southern china, and lowest in non-Chinese rural populations such as Nepal and India.³⁷ The prevalence of myopia in Singapore is one of the highest worldwide.³⁸

3. **Heredity:** Heredity plays an important role in determining ocular refraction, but there is no clear cut mode of inheritance of myopia. It has been documented substantively in studies of monozygotic and dizygotic twins that show that monozygotic twins are much more likely to have similar refractive errors than dizygotic twins.¹²

4. **Family History:** There is a greater prevalence of myopia in children of myopic parents than in children of nonmyopic parents.⁸ Siblings and offspring of a myopic person has, on an average, a three to five times greater chance of being myopic than people without such a myopic relative. However, spouses of a myopic individual were not at significantly increased risk.³⁹

Recently, Zadnic et al. reported that even before the development of myopia, children with two myopic parents had larger eyes and less hyperopic refractive errors than children with one or no myopic parents.⁴⁰

The results of Framingham offspring eye study group, shows strong familial association of myopia between siblings close in age and decreased as the age difference increased.⁴¹

In a parent-offspring study by Yap et al among 7-year-old children, 7.3% were myopic when neither parent was myopic, 26.2% were myopic when one parent was myopic and 45% were myopic when both parents were myopic.⁴²

5. **Gender:** There are significantly lower prevalence rates for male subjects than for female subjects.⁴³ This may perhaps be due to more involvement of females in academic activities than males.

6. **Socioeconomic status:** Economic development and myopia has also been correlated and found that higher the per capita income, higher the incidence of myopia.⁴⁴
7. **Educational level and intelligence:** There is higher prevalence of myopia in persons with higher educational level than in persons with low educational levels. Other studies have shown an association between myopia and intelligence and socio-economic status. Hirsch noted that intelligence test scores could be influenced by the amount of reading a child does or that a more intelligent child might read more and thus become more myopic. Educational level and intelligence are strongly related to amount of close-up work and are probably not independent risk factors but surrogates of close up work.⁸
8. **Effect of environment on myopia:** The most common environmental theory is that if increased scleral stress produced by both the convergence of the extra ocular muscles and the increased tone of the ciliary muscle, each occurs during the accommodative convergence associated with near work. This helps to explain the classic association of the onset of myopia with schooling.
9. **Effect of near work on myopia:** An increased prevalence of myopia is associated with an increased amount of schooling indicates there is a definite role of increased near work as a risk factor for myopia. Near work encompasses tasks of high accommodative demands, such as reading, writing, however it is difficult to separate cause from effect; the study of persons in selected occupational groups who spend large amounts of time on close work may be part of selection process whereby individual with myopia may prefer

these occupations. One of the most widely held theories is the accommodation theory, wherein there is an increase in pressure in the posterior part of the eye during accommodation which is poorly resisted by the sclera, resulting in increased ocular length.⁸

10. Myopia associated with systemic disorders:

- Albinism, Alport's syndrome.
- Down syndrome
- Ehler danlos syndrome.
- Wagner like vitreoretinal degenerations, Congenital rubella, Syringomyelia
- De-Lange syndrome, Riley day syndrome
- Fetal alcohol syndrome.
- Homocystinuria
- Lauren moon bardet-biedl syndrome.
- Marfan's syndrome, Turner syndrome, Noonan syndrome
- Pierre robin syndrome, Seiman syndrome.

11. Myopia associated with ophthalmic disorders:

- Retinitis pigmentosa, Tapetoretinal dystrophies such as Choroideremia, Gyrate atrophy and Pigmentary dystrophy.
- Microphthalmos, Micro cornea, Microphakia, Myelinated nerve fiber.
- Keratoconus, Congenital nystagmus.
- Phlyctenular keratitis and Sclerosing keratitis.
- Buphthalmos, Ectopia lentis

- Coloboma
- Ocular albinism
- Fundus flavimaculatus
- Rod achromatism
- Retinopathy of prematurity
- Glaucoma

Pellucid marginal degeneration

12. Myopia and occupation:

The occurrence of high incidence of myopia in the university students as to the persons not engaged in much near work is suggestive of some relationship between myopia and excessive accommodative effort.

An increased prevalence of myopia is observed in certain occupations, such as microscopy, tailoring, that require a large amount of time spent in close up work.^{8,45}

Studies of persons in occupations involving long hours of close up work, such as textile workers and visual display unit workers, show that the prevalence of myopia is higher in these occupations.^{8,45,46}

Classification of myopia:

1. Classification by rate of myopic progression⁴⁷

- Stationary myopia
- Temporarily progressive myopia
- Permanently progressive myopia

2. Classification by the anatomical features of myopia⁴⁸

- Axial myopia
- Refractive myopia

- Index myopia
 - congenital
 - acquired
- Curvature myopia

3. **Classification based on the degree of myopia**

- Mild myopia < -3.0
- Moderate myopia $- 3.0$ to 6.0 D
- High myopia > -6.0 D

4. Classification into - a) Physiological myopia and b) Pathological myopia

5. Classification into – Hereditary and Environmentally induced myopia

6. Classification according to theory of myopia development

- a) Biological statistical theory
- b) The use abuse theory
- c) The theory of emmetropization

7. Classification based on the age of onset

- a. Congenital myopia
- b. Youth onset myopia
- c. Early adult onset myopia
- d. Late adult onset myopia

8. Duke-elder classification

- a. Simple myopia
- b. Pathological myopia

9. Myopia may also be divided into

- a. Primary myopia

- i. Physiological myopia
 - ii. Intermediate myopia
 - iii. Pathological myopia
 - iv. Curvature myopia
- b. Secondary myopia

10. Curtin classification⁴⁹

- a. Simple
- b. Intermediate
- c. Pathologic

1. Classification by rate of myopic progression

Donders in 1864⁴⁷ classified myopia on the basis of its rate of progression into

- **Stationary myopia:** Is generally of low degree myopia (-1.5 D to -2.0 D) and arises in the years of development. The degree of myopia remains stationary during adulthood and may occasionally diminish with the approach of old age.
- **Temporarily progressive myopia:** Generally arises at the early teens and progresses until the late 20's. After this age, the rate of progression approaches zero.
- **Permanently progressive myopia:** Myopia ascends up rapidly up to 25-35 yrs of age and thereafter advances more slowly. Subsequent increase in myopia are said to occur in jumps, rather than in a smooth progression.

2. Classification by the anatomical features of myopia Borish (1970) stated that myopia could be.

- a) **Axial myopia:** Whereby the eye is too long for its refractive power, results from increase in anteroposterior length of the eyeball. It is the commonest form.⁴⁷
- b) **Refractive myopia:** Where by the refractive system is too powerful for the axial length of the eye. The refractive myopia is further divided into
 - i) **Index myopia:** In which one or more refractive indices of media are anomalous.

Lens index myopia may be of

Congenital origin: The causes are

- Internal lenticonus: It is due to an abnormal convexity of the nucleus
- Increased optical density of the axial portion of the lens (false lenticonus) Congenital nuclear cataract.
- Acquired lens index myopia: Is seen in senile lenticular sclerosis of the nuclei due to increase in refractive index of crystalline lens.⁴⁸
- Curvature myopia: Reduced radius of curvature of one or more refractive surfaces produces increased dioptric power.

Pathological curvature myopia: is seen in

Corneal conditions: Inflammatory diseases – Ulcers & Keratitis.

Ectatic conditions- Keratoconus , pellucid marginal degeneration, keratoglobus.

Lenticular conditions:

- Microphakia
- Spherophakia
- Microphthalmos
- Ectopia lentis
- Subluxation
- Dislocation
- Anterior lenticonus
- Lentiglobus
- Posterior lenticonus

Anterior chamber depth myopia: Decrease in anterior chamber depth increases the refractive power of the eye.

3. Classification based on the degree of myopia:

- a) Mild myopia: $< -3D$
- b) Moderate myopia: $-3D$ to $-6 D$
- c) High myopia: $> - 6 D$

4. Classification into physiological and pathological myopias:

a) Physiological myopia- Was defined by Curtis (1985)⁴⁷ as myopia in which each component of refraction lies within the normal distribution for that population. Thus myopia arises from a failure of correlation between the refractive components.

b) Pathological myopia – Duke-elders & Abrams (1970)⁴⁷ defined Pathological myopia as those refractive anomalies determined by the presence in the optical system of the eye of an element which lies outside the limits of the normal biological

variations. Pathological myopia may also be described as malignant or degenerative myopia.

These authors adopted the term degenerative myopia to describe myopia that is accompanied by degenerative changes, particularly in the posterior segment of the globe. This is more frequently found in high degrees of myopia. (> 6D), but Duke-Elder and Abrams suggested that a classification merely by degree of ametropia is inappropriate because degenerative changes may also occur in cases of low myopia.

5. Classification into hereditary and environmentally induced myopia:

The debate of hereditary versus environmental influences on the development of myopia has persisted, and is still unresolved. Rosenfield (1994) noted that the case for such an association remains unproven.⁴⁷ It is frequently impossible to distinguish between environmental and hereditary influences and hence other means of classification have been adopted.

6. Classification according to theory of myopia development:

In a review of the etiology of refractive error, McBrien and Barnes (1984) described three major theories of myopic development.⁴⁷

- a. Biological statistical theory:** Steiger in 1913 considered variations in refractive error as forming a biological continuum ranging from high myopia to high hyperopia. Thus ametropia simply represented the normal biological variation of a physiological component.
- b. The use abuse theory:** Proposed by Cohn (1886) suggested that myopia onset was an adaptation to use or abuse of the eyes during sustained near vision. He observed in the youngest children there was little myopia but the prevalence increased with age. He concluded that because the increased prevalence of

myopia occurred during the educational process, a substantial portion of which entailed reading and other close work, the onset of myopia was related to increase near vision activities. However, other factors such as intelligence and changes towards the western diet are also partly responsible for the change in refractive error distribution in this population.

- c. **The theory of emmetropization:** The components of the eye do not grow independently, but rather undergo a process of coordinated growth. This proposed correlated growth of the ocular biometric components has been referred to as emmetropization (Straub, 1909, cited by Hofstetter 1969). The emmetropization was achieved by a negative feedback, self focusing control system. Variations in ciliary muscle tone could produce changes in refractive error by interfering with this self focusing mechanism.

7. Classification based on the age of Onset:

Grosvenor (1987) classified myopia into the following categories.^{47,50}

- a. **Congenital myopia:** Myopia is present at birth and persists through infancy. But it is usually diagnosed by the age of 2-3 yrs.⁴⁸ It is seen more frequently in prematurely born children or with various birth defects, such as marfan's syndrome and homocystinuria. Most of the time myopia is unilateral. It is usually associated with an increase in axial length and overall globe size. It may be associated with congenital convergent squint. Usually the error is of about 8-10 Dioptres, which mostly remains constant. It may be associated with other congenital anomalies such as cataract microphthalmos, aniridia, megalocornea and congenital separation of retina. The child will have difficulty in seeing the distant objects and will hold the things very close for viewing. Unilateral congenital myopia is frequently discovered either by

routine screening examination or after a strabismus develops because of the associated amblyopia. Early correction of congenital myopia is desirable to help the child to develop normal distant vision, and perception of the world. The full cycloplegic refractive error including any astigmatic correction should be prescribed. Achieving 6/6 vision is very difficult. The prognosis for good vision and normal binocularity is poor in unilateral cases if the anisometropia and myopia are severe. The prevalence of this form of myopia, which is usually of sufficient amount to persist throughout life, is about 2%.

- b. Youth onset myopia:** The onset of myopia occurs between 6 years of age and the early teens. During this period, the prevalence of myopia (of 0.50 D or more) increases from about 2% at 6 to about 20% at age 20. A large percentage of youth-onset myopes have a relatively small amount of myopia, and many of them will become emmetropic or even hyperopic in later years, with result that the prevalence of this form of myopia would be expected to decrease during adult years.
- c. Early adult onset myopia:** Onset of myopia occurs between 20 and 40 yrs of age and brings the prevalence of myopia to about 30% during this period of life. Many of those will have only a small amount of myopia and will become emmetropic or even hyperopic in their later years.
- d. Late adult onset myopia:** Myopia onset occurs after 40 yrs of age, with the prevalence gradually increasing in the later years of life. The major cause of this form of myopia is incipient nuclear cataracts.

8. Duke-Elder classification:

a. Simple Myopia:

Simple or developmental myopia is the commonest variety. It is considered as the physiological error not associated with any disease of the eye. Its prevalence increases from 2% at 5 yrs to 14% at 15 yrs of age. Since the sharpest rise occurs at school going age that is between 8 yrs to 12 yrs, so it is also called as school myopia.^{33, 48}

Etiology: It results from normal biological variation in the development of eye which may or may not be genetically determined. Some factors associated with simple myopia are as follows.

- Axial type: May signify just a physiological variation in the length of the eyeball.
- Curvatural type
- Role of diet: In early childhood has also been reported.⁴⁸
- Role of genetics - Genetics plays some role in the biological variation of the development of eye, as prevalence of myopia is more in children with both parents myopic (20%) than the children with one parent myopic (10%) and children with no parent myopic (5%).⁴⁸
- Theory of excessive near work in childhood was also put forward.

Clinical picture:**Symptoms:**

- Poor vision for distance (Short-Sightedness) is the main symptom of myopia.
- Asthenopic symptoms-with small degree of myopia like eye strain, headache, early fatigue
- Half shutting of the eyes may be complained by parents of the child.
- Holding books near while reading
- Squint, photophobia,
- Rubbing of eyes.
- Repeated attacks of Hordeolum externum, Hordeolum internum and Chalazion.
- Floaters occasionally.
- Night blindness
- Contraction of visual fields.
- Scotoma.

Signs:

- Prominent eyeballs, large cornea,
- Deep anterior chamber
- Pupils – large and a bit sluggishly reacting to light.
- Fundus is normal, rarely temporal myopic crescent may be seen.

Magnitude of refractive error:

Simple myopia usually occurs between 5-10 yrs of age and it keeps on increasing till about 18-20 yrs of age, at a rate of about -0.50 ± 0.30 every year. Usually the error doesn't exceed 6 to 8 Dioptres.

Diagnosis: Is confirmed by performing retinoscopy.

b. Pathological myopia:

Degenerative / Progressive myopia, as the name indicates, is a rapidly progressive error which starts in childhood at 5-10 yrs of age and results in high myopia during early adult life, which is usually associated with degenerative changes in the eye.

The condition is frequently termed progressive myopia; but as the habit of hypermetropia is to regress during development, so the majority of myopes, most of them of the simple type-progress. High myopia (for example, above -6D) is inappropriate to say pathological/ degenerative myopia. On ophthalmoscopy it should show typical pathologic findings of myopia. Sometimes even low myopes may show degenerative changes characteristic of myopia, while cases over -17D may show no abnormal changes in the fundus (Harman, 1913).

Etiology: It results from a rapid axial growth of the eye ball which is outside the normal biological variations of development. It is linked with hereditary and general growth process.

1. Role of heredity:

Genetic factors play a major role in the etiology as the progressive myopia is

- i. Familial
- ii. More common in certain races like Chinese, Japanese, Arabs and Jews,
and

iii. Uncommon among Negroes, Nubians and Sudanese.

It is presumed that heredity-linked growth of retina is the determinant in the development of myopia. The sclera, due to its distensibility follows the retinal growth, but the choroid undergoes degeneration due to stretching, which in turn causes degeneration of retina.

2. **Role of general growth process:** Lengthening of the posterior segment of the globe commences only during the period of active growth, and ends with the termination of the active growth. Therefore, the factors (such as nutritional deficiency, debilitating diseases, endocrinal disturbances and indifferent general health), which affect the general growth process will also influence the progression of myopia.

The etiological hypothesis for pathological myopia is summarized below.

Degree of pathological myopia: High myopia may frequently attain an extent of -20D, and cases up to -30D are not very unusual. The highest record found in the literature is RE-60D, LE-24D; apart from small myopic crescent both fundi were normal and vision with full correction was 3/60, 6/60 respectively. High degrees of astigmatism are not uncommonly associated with myopia.

Binocular inequality of myopia:

An unequal degree of high myopia in the two eyes is so common as to be almost the rule, but gross inequalities (greater than 3D) are relatively rare. The most dramatic asymmetry is in the occurrence of unilateral high myopia, which is relatively rare. An analysis of the figures from the literature tends to show predominance for the higher degrees of myopia or for the unilateral myopia to be in the right eye. As in many other cases of marked anisometropia, in unilateral myopia the affected eye is often amblyopic and eccentric fixation is common; only a small percentage can be expected to attain useful binocular vision even with the aid of contact lenses and prolonged pleoptic treatment lasting for periods even up to three years.

Clinical features:

Symptoms: ^{12, 51}

- Defective vision for distance and uncorrectable loss of vision may occur due to progressive degenerative changes.
- Muscae volitantes that is floating black opacities in front of the eyes are also complained of by many patients. These occur due to degenerated liquefied vitreous.
- Night blindness-Complained by very high myopes having marked degenerative changes.

- Repeated attacks of Hordeolum externum, Hordeolum internum & Chalazion.
- Contraction of visual fields.
- Children hold books near while reading.
- Scotoma
- Rubbing of the eyes.
- Asthenopic symptoms, early fatigue, headache and watering.
- Reduced contrast sensitivity.^{52,53}

Signs:

- Prominent eyeballs: Elongation of the eyeball mainly affects the posterior pole and the surrounding area; the part of the eye anterior to the equator may be normal (fig. 3).

Fig 3: Elongation of the eyeball posterior to the equator in pathological myopia

- Cornea is large and curvature will be more.
- Refractive index of the lens may be increased and it may be moved anteriorly.
- Anterior chamber is deep.
- Pupils are slightly large and react sluggishly to light

- Axial length is increased
- Angle Kappa: Angle Kappa is the angle between visual axis and pupillary axis. In emmetropic eyes it is positive and negative in high myopia.

Fundus Changes in Myopia:

Distant direct ophthalmoscopy :- The patients with high myopia have a dark fundal glow.²⁵

i. Optic disc changes:

- a) Tilted disc
- b) Large disc
- c) Pale disc
- d) Large cup
- e) C/D ratio is more
- f) Crescents
 - Temporal
 - Nasal
 - Superior
 - Inferior
 - Annular
- g) Super traction (Superevolution)
 - Nasal
 - Temporal

ii. Macular changes:

- a) Foster Fuchs spot
- b) Laquer cracks

- c) Subretinal neovascularisation (SRNV)
- d) Sub retinal hemorrhage
- e) Chorioretinal degeneration
- f) Extension of temporal crescent

iii. Retinal changes:

- a) Tessellated fundus
- b) Chorioretinal degeneration
- c) Staphyloma
- d) Stretch schisis
- e) Pits
- f) Choroidal neovascularisation
- g) White without pressure.

iv. Peripheral retinal changes:

- Lattice degeneration
- Pavingstone degeneration
- Pigmentary degeneration
- White without pressure
- Snail track degeneration
- Retinal breaks.
- Peripheral cystoid degeneration
- Chorioretinal degeneration
- Acquired retinoschisis

Optic disc changes

The striking changes at the optic disc have excited much attention and stimulated much controversy. The classical investigations of Heine (1899) showed

that the myopic disc had a straight cribriform plate with a very thin layer of pre-cribriform glial tissue which Goldmann (1957) estimated at less than half the thickness of the non-myopic eye.

The optic disc is large in the myopic eye. It is interesting that the ratio of the optic cup to the optic disc has been found by Armaly (1967) to be genetically determined in a multifactorial pattern showing no influence of age or sex. Tomlinson and Philips (1969) have found, however that it does vary with the axial length of the eye, the ratio tending to be high when this was long and the refraction myopic, but low in the short hypermetropic eye. It would be seen that the absolute area of the disc varies with the size of the eyeball but that the volume of nerve fibers congregated at the nerve head is relatively constant.

The myopic crescent (conus myopicus)

May be present at birth (Von Jaeger, 1855) but usually becomes evident about puberty; at the age of 16 years it is common, and becomes almost invariable in later years in myopia over -6D (Donders 1864).

Common site of myopic crescent is on temporal side but it can occur superiorly, inferiorly and/ or all around the disc. It may even involve the macula (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Myopic crescent

The crescents are not only seen or confined to myopia but also present in normal emmetropic eyes, hypermetropic eyes and in astigmatism. In astigmatism the greatest refraction lying in the direction of the crescent.

The nerve fibers usually traverse the disc in an obliquely nasal direction, and at the nerve-head many variations may be observed. The choroid usually terminates some distance from the margin of the disc and is completely or partially absent in the area of the crescent. Bruch's membrane may terminate with it; it may persist well towards the disc or, conversely, may end some distance from the edge of the choroid.

The outer retinal layers and the pigmentary epithelium may be absent in the area of the crescent and only the inner layers continue. As they dip into the disc, where the retina overlaps the choroid the outer retinal nerve fibers often form a definite loop, running outwards beneath the retina and then turning back at a sharp angle to reach the optic nerve.

The incidence of myopic crescent directly varies with the axial length, usually present in high myopia.

Causes of formation of myopic crescent

May be developmental, being determined in the foetal life. This is according to Schanabel (1874), Elschmig (1903-1905) and VonSzily (1922) believed that the crescent, like the conus, was determined in foetal life, but this assumption lacks proof and there is no evidence that the coloboma-like appearances formed in foetal life develop into progressive defects in adults.

According to Schanabel (1874) it is caused simply by stretching, the choroid being dragged back into the ectasia at the posterior pole of the eye.

According to Vogt, 1924 and Stacker 1943 it may be due to excessive response by the sclera to the stimulation of retinal growth so that a gap is left between the border of the choroid and the disc.

According to Salzmann (1902), it is due to localized atrophy.

Other causes are

- Backward pull by the optic nerve (Weiss, 1982-84)
- Due to the pull of the superior oblique muscle (Stilling, 1985-1905)
- Pull of the ciliary muscle in accommodation (Iwanoff 1869)
- Super traction of the retina (Superevolution):

Super traction of the retina over the nasal side of the disc was first described by Von Jaeger (1861), in small number of cases, there will be super traction of the retina over the nasal side of the disc, blurring of the disc margin, the disc vessel bending over the curved edge, sometimes almost halfway across the papilla.

Rarely myopic crescent appears on nasal side, and super traction appears on temporal side (Inverse myopia).

Alternatively, it is due to retinal overgrowth which on the nasal side finds no expansive outlet comparable with the posterior pole on the temporal side. It is also to be remembered that, supervolution of the retina, as is the case with most myopic changes, is also found in non-myopic eyes.

A crescent light reflex known as **Weiss otto reflex** may become apparent on the nasal aspect of the disc. This reflex result from crescentic pilling up of nasal retina and choroids and best appreciated in young patients.

The peripapillary crescent correlated with increasing axial length but not total refractive power of the eye.

The myopic crescent in physiological myopia is usually $1/3$ DD; in high myopia it will increase to more than $1/3$ DD.

The crescent may have pigmentation on the inner aspect of the sclera, but crescent may have appearance of bare sclera.

Myopic crescent and super traction may result from abnormal asymmetric growth of temporal part of the sclera.

Macular Changes

a. Foster Fuchs Spot

A round elliptical black lesion known as fuchs spot may occur in pathological myopia usually in the macula. First described by Foster (1862), first anatomically examined by Lehmus (1875) and extensively studied by E. Fuchs (1901). The black lesion is Sharp, circumscribed, slightly elevated with variable size (Fig. 5). These develop after the age of 35 years. They are found in 10% of high myopia. It is due to

proliferation of the pigmented epithelium possibly associated with a chroidal hemorrhage. 40% of cases it is bilateral, with the second eye becoming affected within 5 years. It appears in 4th or 5th decade in moderately high myopes (about or above -12D).

Fig. 5: Foster Fuchs spot

They appear in an area overlying chroidal neovascular membrane and appear as hyperplasia of RPE. Fibrosis may occur over the spot, imparting grey, yellow, green and red appearance to the lesion.

With time, spot becomes less distinct and a halo of atrophy may develop around it. Similar lesions can develop in absence of myopia.

The presence of Fuchs spot is a poor prognostic sign. These areas subsequently lead to widespread chorioretinal degeneration. Foster Fuchs Spot distorts central vision and later causes central scotoma.

b. Laquer cracks

Laquer cracks are yellow white lines of variable caliber found deep to retina in posterior pole, having fine irregular caliber with horizontal branching. They are frequently multiple. Large choroidal vessels may be seen traversing them.

Usually they don't produce any field defects and doesn't leak on fundus fluoresceine angiography. Their presence is a poor prognostic sign. Extensive degenerative changes may occur in that area.

These laquer cracks probably develop due to mechanical stretching of the eyes. The role of primary degeneration cannot be excluded.

Histopathological examination

They correspond to area of fissuring in RPE, Bruch's membrane and choriocapillaries. Extensive laquer cracks may be associated with macular hemorrhages.

Laquer cracks are linear or stellate; the lines are fine irregular in caliber yellow white in colour, horizontally oriented, may be single or multiple, often branching with crisscrossing, located deeper to retina, borders are pigmented when they are larger, choroidal vessels are seen. There is no irregularity or distortion of retina, or retinal vessels, may connect to temporal crescent, if numerous cracks are present may show reticular fishnet fashion. The occurrence or extension of laquer cracks can be associated with macular hemorrhage.

c. Subretinal neovascularisation: (SRNV)

Occurs in 5-10% of myopic population with high myopia - SRNV usually exhibits a small juxtafoveal grey lesion with a shallow overlying retinal detachment and subretinal hemorrhage.

With time, there are unusual pigmentary response results in Fuchs spot. Results in RPE hyperplasia over the SRNV. Visual acuity stabilizing over an acute decrease in vision associated with SRNV, related to subretinal hemorrhage (Fosters spot)

Retinal changes

Peripheral retinochoroidal atrophy

Is characterized by numerous small patches of atrophy and pigmentary proliferation anterior to the equator, but is not peculiar to this refractive condition. The picture corresponds to that of peripheral cystic degeneration of the retina which is an almost constant occurrence in senility and may also be seen in the young; it is a common feature of myopic eyes, in which condition it may occur in comparatively early part of life. Retinal holes may also occur, but such degenerative changes are by no means invariable.

Scleral ectasias are relatively frequent in the higher degrees of myopia. Irregularities in the depth of the fundus so that differences of refraction exist in various localities are not very uncommon, particularly around the disc in the presence of a crescent, but the formation of a localized ectasia in the region of the posterior pole presents a striking ophthalmoscopic picture. This was first described by Von Graefe (1854) as “staphyloma posticum verum”, but little attention was given to its occurrence and nature until interest was resuscitated by Weiss (1888), de-Wecker and Masselon (1891), Otto (1891-98) and Casper (1894). Sometimes the fundus dips down into the ectasia gradually but more usually there is a relatively abrupt edge, the shadow of which appears

Ophthalmoscopically as a dark line over which the retinal vessels bend and sometimes disappear from view as at the edge of a glaucomatous cup. Occasionally the edge appears as a rounded ridge over which the vessels bulge. Between the main levels of the fundus and the depths of the crater there may be a large dioptric difference, frequently of the order of 10D and, while the texture of the fundus in general may be good, there may be much chorioretinal atrophy in the staphyloma

itself so that it has an albinotic appearance with the choroidal vessels distinctly delineated.

In the majority of cases staphyloma involves the posterior pole of the eye, but the most common site for a sharp crescentic line of shadow is to the nasal side of the disc. The sharp shadow indicates an extension nasally of the ectasia at the posterior pole: occasionally the line is duplicated as the depression descends in one or more steps (Sattler 1907). In other cases where the staphyloma is more accentuated, a circular line may be apparent, circumscribing a pit at the bottom of which lies the optic disc usually surrounded by an annular crescent. Rarely an ectasia is limited to the nasal side of the disc. Congenital ectasia is not very uncommon, for which a typical site is below the disc.

Curtin (1985)⁵⁰ has described several types of posterior staphylomas, based on their location with regard to the optic nerve head and the macula: they are as follows:

The type I staphyloma (the most common, located at the posterior pole) is evidenced by a horizontally elliptical area of pallor and tessellation encompassing both the optic nerve head and the macular area.

The type II staphyloma (the second most common) is smaller than type I staphyloma, with the area of pallor and tessellation extending to the optic nerve head but not the macular area.

The type III, the least common of four types, has a small area of tessellation encompassing the optic nerve head but not the macular area.

The type IV is a nasal, or inverse, staphyloma, extending nasally (rather than temporally) from the optic nerve head.

Fig. 6: Types of Posterior staphyloma.

Degenerative changes in vitreous:

Changes in the vitreous are almost constant occurrence in myopia, frequently appearing at an early stage and usually becoming more accentuated in latter life. Myopic degeneration of the vitreous closely resembles the senile type: the gel liquefies first at the posterior pole and the area immediately behind the lens is seen with the slit-lamp to be crowded with nodular interlacing filaments behind which fibrillar diaphanous membranes are visible (microfibrillar degeneration). The opacities are aggregations of the colloid basis of the gel indicating its disruption without serious implications, but they give rise to distressing entoptic opacities.

A posterior detachment of the vitreous is a common feature of myopia, described by Iwanoff (1869) as a “detachment vacuo”, the stretching of the globe leaving a space between the face of the vitreous and the posterior pole of the eye.

On ophthalmoscopic examination the posterior surface of the gel gives rise to the reflex originally described by Weiss (1885-97) and details of the detachment can be clearly seen with the slit-lamp aided by a contact lens.

The “**reflex streak of Weiss**” was considered by him to be the first ophthalmoscopic sign of early myopia. He described it as a brilliant, crescentic, finely striated reflex on the nasal side of the disc, particularly evident by the direct ophthalmoscopy. It occurs in advanced myopia and is sometimes seen in non-myopic eyes when detachment of the vitreous occurs. Although it is most readily seen on the nasal side of the disc, by manipulating the light it can be made to appear on the temporal side, and may, indeed become evident as a circle anywhere around the posterior pole of the eye completely dissociated from the optic disc; this can be made particularly evident in fundus photography. Stereoscopic photography shows it to be localized in front of the retina.

A further appearance at the posterior pole is condensation of the vitreous face into a grey membranous opacity, frequently taking the form of a ring indicating where it has become detached from the disc. The opacity floats about in front of the disc and may take on many shapes; but it is not characteristic of myopia, appearing commonly in senility or in any part of the fundus associated with a localized patch of degeneration or inflammation.

Peripheral retinal changes: Include

- Lattice degeneration: Myopic eyes have an increased predisposition for Retinal Detachment. It occurs in approximately 1/4th of myopic eyes.
- Pigmentary degeneration.

- White without pressure
- Snailtract degeneration
- Pavingstone degeneration
- Retinal breaks
- White with pressure
- Peripheral cystoid degeneration
- Chorioretinal degeneration
- Acquired retinoschisis.

Visual fields:

- Central scotoma
- Irregular enlargement of blind spot.
- Peripheral constriction of visual fields.
- Ring scotoma.
- Hemianopia.
- Isolated Scotoma.

These correspond to chorioretinal degeneration.

- ERG – Is subnormal due to choroidal atrophy.
- EOG – Is abnormal.

Complications of degenerative myopia:

The complications of degenerative myopia are numerous and grave, for the disability frequently results in blindness. As with the degenerative changes themselves, the complications appear typically in adult life after the myopia has been fully established for some years.

Choroidal thrombosis and hemorrhages are not infrequent, as would be expected in view of the early obliteration of the small vessels. Such hemorrhages may be recurrent and when they occur in the central area, as they habitually do, each leading to the formation or extension of scarred atrophic areas, their cumulative effect upon vision is frequently disastrous, even if they are individually small. Large hemorrhages are correspondingly more tragic.

Vitreous opacities, always present in some degree in high myopia, may suddenly increase to become a serious complication. They may be either endogenous to the vitreous, a cloud of opacities or membranous veils appearing suddenly as the gel liquefies, or a leakage from a choroidal vessel may fill the vitreous with blood.

Retinal detachment: Is the most dreaded and one of the most common complication of myopia, occurring with considerable frequency in all degrees of the defect but showing a progressively greater tendency in higher degree of myopia. This association was first stressed by Von Graefe (1857) who found that 50-60% of detachments occurred in myopic eyes. Summarizing the literature between 1879 and 1914, Leber (1916) found that 65% of retinal detachments occurred in myopes, and the estimate that $2/3^{\text{rds}}$ of all detachments occur in this refractive condition has been verified by the experience of surgeons from most countries since that time and in more than half of these cases no other cause can be found. Moreover a retinal detachment occurs earlier in the myopic population than in those with other refractive conditions; it is more frequently bilateral and is relatively more common in eyes with the higher degrees of myopia. It is interesting that Gonin (1934) found the two commonest ocular degenerations, myopia and senility were together responsible for 85% of retinal detachments.

The higher the refractive error, the greater is the risk of RD. The following interrelated factors predispose a myopic eye to RD.

Lattice degeneration: Is more common in moderate myopes, and may give rise to either tears or atrophic holes. Giant retinal tears may also develop along the posterior edge of long lattice islands.

Snail track degeneration: Is common in myopic eyes and may be associated with atrophic holes.

Diffuse chorioretinal atrophy may give rise to small round holes in myopic eyes.

Macular holes may give rise to RD in highly myopic eyes, particularly those with a posterior staphyloma.

Vitreous degeneration and PVD – are more common

Vitreous loss during cataract surgery, particularly if inappropriately managed, is associated with an increased risk of subsequent RD, particularly in highly myopic eyes.

Laser posterior capsulotomy is associated with an increased risk of RD in High myopic eyes.⁵⁴

Common etiological factor for the occurrence of detachment in myopia is the formation of a retinal hole in an atrophic area, particularly in the periphery of the fundus where this process is facilitated by the occurrence of cystic degeneration and is aided by the adherence of the framework of the degenerated vitreous.

Simple glaucoma is a further complication of considerable importance in high myopia, A significant percentage of cases of glaucoma usually of the slow, insidious and chronic type occurs in high myopes, most observers giving a figure of about 14% (Priestley Smith, 1879; Weinstein, 1934; Lehrfeld and Reber, 1937; Weekers et.al

1958) while others give a higher percentage (29%, Carvill, 1932; 43%, Lange, 1896; 33% Lacroix, 1922); 56.6% H. Goldschmidt, 1923; 28% Diaz-Doningeuz 1961).

Many cases have been recorded in high myopia. It may be accepted that the incidence of simple glaucoma is certainly not less than in the nonmyopic population. In fact, any insidious deterioration of vision in a case of high myopia, even in a relatively young patient, which is not otherwise explained, should give rise to the suspicion of the presence of this disease. The relation between the two conditions is not clear. Some writers suggest that the raised intraocular pressure determines or accentuates the myopia; others maintain that high myopia and glaucoma are of the same degenerative nature; while a third view is that the glaucoma is sequelae to generalized atrophy of the choroid. Podos and his colleagues (1966) suggested that a genetic linkage existed between glaucoma and high myopia.

Whatever the relationship, the frequent occurrence of glaucoma in high myopia is clear, and the clinical importance of the association lies in the fact that the glaucoma is usually of an insidious type without high tension and therefore readily missed by indentation tonometry. The appearance of the optic disc is also frequently misleading owing to the thinness of the pre-cribriform glial tissue. It is true that a typical concave cup with overhanging edges may be present, but more frequently the cup is shallow with a sharp or even a gradually slanting edge giving the appearance that the disc is merely participating in the posterior staphyloma. This shallowness of the cup, indeed, may resemble the appearance of the disc in myopia without glaucoma, so that a differentiation can be made only by further investigation to establish the presence of a raised tension.

Cataract – Is a further complication of high myopia, occurring particularly in the higher degrees after mid life; typically it is of the posterior polar type and is

frequently associated with degenerative conditions of the choroid. Nuclear lens changes may also occur, leading initially to a further aggravation of the myopic refraction.

Myopia, particularly high myopia, seems to have inhibitory influence on hypertensive and diabetic retinopathies. Vascular obstructions are slightly less frequent and papilloedema is much marked in these persons. And angle closure glaucoma is less frequent.

9. Myopia may also be divided into

Primary myopia: This is again divided into:

- I. Physiological myopia
- II. Intermediate myopia
- III. Pathological myopia
- IV. Curvature myopia.

Secondary myopia: Described as eyes that have myopic refraction as a result of well defined abnormalities in specific tissues of the eye eg: Buphthalmos, Intumescent cataract, corneal edema secondary to trauma, certain corneal dystrophies, prolonged use of rigid contact lens, prolonged or continuous accommodation for high degree of hypermetropia may result in accommodative spasm leading to pseudomyopia. Scleral buckling and phototherapeutic keratotomy done for peripheral and paracentral opacity with laser may steepen the central cornea leading to myopia.

10. Curtin Classification of myopia:

TABLE 2: Curtin Classification⁵⁰

	Simple	Intermediate	Pathologic
Synonyms	Physiologic myopia, School myopia , Low myopia	Low myopia	Degenerative myopia, Malignant myopia, High myopia
Refractive range (D)	-0.25 D to -5.00 D	-3.00 D to -10.00 D	-8.00 D to -30.0D
Cornea	Normal	Normal	Normal to steep
AC depth	Normal	Normal	Normal to deep
Lens	Normal	Normal	Normal to steep
AXL(mm)	Normal (22-25)	Normal (24-32)	Very elongated >30
Posterior fundus appearance	Normal	Scleral crescent, Tesselated	Scleral crescent, tessellated, posterior staphyloma
Associated ocular disease	Few	Few	Chronic open angle glaucoma, peripheral retinal degeneration, RD , macular degeneration, Breaks in bruch's membrane, Chrioretinal atrophy.

Acquired Myopia

It is a much greater problem because almost one third of the population in an industrialized society will become myopic after several years of schooling or during adult years.

Pseudomyopia

It has been defined as a reversible form of myopia that results from a spasm of the ciliary muscle (Grosvenor, 1989).^{47, 50}

Sato (1957) and other researchers have contended, however, that myopia occurs as a result of “ciliary spasm”. As a result of prolonged accommodation, the ciliary muscle is thought to increase in tonicity to the point where it fails to fully relax when distance vision is attempted. The excessive accommodative response produces an apparent myopic shift that will disappear when a cycloplegic agent is administered to produce relaxation of accommodation. In the beginning stages of myopia, the individual may complain that distance vision blur following prolonged near work and asthenopia but that it clears up after a few minutes. The amount of myopia is probably no more than about 1.00 D.

Some drugs like acetazolamide, aspirin, corticosteroids, isosorbide, morphine, phenothiazines, spironolactones, and sulphonamides can cause ciliary spasm. In diabetes mellitus osmotic swelling of the lens can cause reversible myopia.

Accommodative spasm in systemic diseases like myasthenia gravis, encephalitis, and syphilis can lead to temporary myopic state.

Pseudomyopia can be managed by modification of working distance, temporary low myopic prescription or through appropriate ocular exercises.

Night myopia

The phenomenon of increased myopia under low-luminance conditions was first reported in 1789 by the Reverend Nevil Maskelyne, the Astronomer Royal.^{47,50} He found that his astronomical observations at night were facilitated by the use of concave spectacle lenses. Maskelyne reported, “To see day objects with most distinctness, I require a less concave lens by ‘one degree’ (between 0.37 and 1 D) than for seeing the stars in best by night”.

Night myopia is produced by an increased accommodative response (typically on the order of 0.5 to 1.00 D) under degraded stimulus conditions. Also changes in chromatic aberration may be involved in this myopic shift. The chromatic aberration of the eye results in blue light with wavelength of 555 nm more than red light with wavelength 510 nm during which eye transfers from photopic to scotopic luminance level. This change in sensitivity is termed as Purkinje shift. Thus at extremely low luminance levels, the eye becomes more sensitive to those wavelengths undergoing a greater degree of refraction and therefore appears to be more myopic than it is under photopic viewing conditions.

Some authors confirmed that the change in the dioptric power of the eye results directly from a shift in accommodation that is a change in the refractive power of the crystalline lens.

At night, there is a shift towards more myopia, as a large pupil exposes the more peripheral portion of the lens, which tends to have more plus power (spherical aberration). The Styles-Crawford effect, a notion that the photoreceptor, acting as wave guides, are less sensitive to photons striking them obliquely, is involved to argue that the peripheral optics of the eye are relatively unimportant.⁶¹

Index myopia

It seen in following circumstances:

- Nuclear sclerosis: in this condition nucleus becomes more and more hyper-refrangent pari passu, with which develops a progressive myopia.
- Incipient cataract may also cause index myopia.
- Diabetic myopia occurs due to a decrease in the refractive index of cortex.

Transient myopia:

1. Due to various toxic states, such as
 - Jaundice
 - Influenza
2. Prolonged use of eye for short focal distances.
3. Irradiation
4. Prolonged diarrhea
5. Profuse sweating
6. Alkalosis
7. Myopia associated with menstruation
8. As a sequelae to external inflammation like
 - Episcleritis
 - Scleritis

Due to reflex ciliary irritation
9. Pressure on the globe: Myopia may occur due to pressure over the equatorial region.
10. Following Local conditions may lead to myopia due to irritative spasm of the ciliary muscle.

- Iritis
- Cyclitis
- Iridocyclitis.

Traumatic myopia:

Extent of Myopia varies from 1 to 6 Dioptres, but its duration of onset may vary from days to weeks, most of the cases it is transient, clearing up in a week or two. The refraction returns to normal in the great majority of cases within a month. If myopia is induced by spasm of ciliary muscle, atropine should be instilled.

Causes:

- Ciliary spasm
- Weakening or rupture of zonules
- Subluxation of lens.
- Dislocation of lens
- Cataractous changes in the lens
- Forward displacement of lens.
- Lengthening of anteroposterior diameter of the globe due to trauma.

Space myopia:

This condition is experienced when the individual has no stimulation for distance fixation.

The eyes tend to choose a near fixation plane which can be very variable. The degree of myopia due to this condition is never more than 0.75 – 1.5 D. It is particularly troublesome to aviators when flying in cloud or fog or at night.

Drug-induced myopia:

Due to administration of drugs like

- Arsenicals
- Sulfonamides
- Adreno corticotrophic hormone
- Prednisolone
- Antihistamines
- Prochlorpromazine
- Penicillamine
- Oral contraceptives
- Cholinergic drugs such as pilocarpine, echothiophate and di-isopropyl fluorophosphates.

Instrumental myopia or Microscope myopia:

It is form of myopia that occurs when someone is looking into an optical Instrument such as a microscope. The person focuses his or her eyes closer than needed for the image produced by the instrument.

When someone looks into an optical instrument, such as microscope, Vision is far from ordinary. A microscope might force the person to use only one eye, it presents the person with a limited field of view, it presents a magnified view, and it allows the person to adjust the focus of the instrument for any viewing distance. Ideally, the person will choose a focus adjustment on the instrument that allows the eyes to have relaxed accommodation – that is to present the objects at a distance of about 6 meters, or optical infinity.

However, most people tend to accommodate to nearer than 6 meter. it is this too close focusing of the eyes that is instrument myopia. Accommodating to a distance nearer than 6 meters makes the ciliary muscles work harder than they need to, leading to fatigue. Some binocular microscopes are designed so that the vergence of the eyes is correct for 6-meter viewing distance.

According to Wesner and Miller (1986), instrument myopia is promoted when the viewing is with one eye, when the field of view is small, and when the luminance is low.

Wesner and Miller also said it is possible that a person's knowledge that the viewed object is very close contributes to instrument myopia.

MANAGEMENT OF MYOPIA

Optical treatment of myopia constitutes prescription of appropriate concave lenses, so that clear image is formed on the retina. Apart from the elimination of any pathological changes in the fundus, the eyes should be examined at frequent intervals to assess the significance of any progress, particularly when a hereditary tendency to myopia is shown.

1) Visual rehabilitation

a) Optical correction by

- Spectacle lenses
- Contact lenses
- Low visual aids

b) Surgical correction by³⁵

- Radial keratotomy
- Photorefractive keratectomy
- Laser in-situ keratomileusis

- Clear lens extraction
- Phakic IOL
- Intracorneal ring implantation
- Orthokeratology
- Epikeratophakia

2) Prevention of myopic progression

- a) General supportive measures
- b) Modification of ocular use
- c) Contact lens

3) Prophylaxis

MANAGEMENT OF MYOPIA

The aim of management of simple myopia is visual rehabilitation and prevention of myopic progression. Myopic eyes should be thoroughly examined. Ocular motility, IOP measurement and fundus examination is mandatory, to have a baseline observation. Retinoscopy should be done under cycloplegia, and for the patients under the age of 6 yrs, atropine ointment is preferred.

The prescription of spectacles for young myopic subjects is psychologically important, with their optical defect uncorrected, they develop in a limited world wherein they are at a considerable disadvantage in comparison with others, a handicap which may entail a seeming limitation of intelligence and a curtailment of interests which are frequently ascribed to stupidity and backwardness, or to naughtiness, while they are really due to the physical defect; avoiding outdoor sports and prone to introspection, debarred from free mixing with their fellows and unable to enjoy a full appreciation of life; they frequently tend to grow up with introverted mental habits and peculiarities.

Poor vision and inability to read the material on the blackboard can have a serious impact on a child's participation and learning in class and this can adversely affect the child's education, occupation and socio-economic status for life.

The problem of poor vision due to myopia is so prevalent that it does not only interfere with the children's ability to attend classes and study, but also creates grave social consequences. Teachers who do not realize the plight of the problem, for example, accuse them persistently. Unsympathetic classmates also pester them and laugh at them in the classrooms as well as in the playgrounds. Even their parents and siblings undermine and discourage this unfortunate children.⁵⁶

Lower contrast sensitivity as observed with myopes is associated with impaired perception of “real world targets,”⁵⁷ poorer flight performance in aircraft simulators⁵⁸ and deficits in visual spatial attention.⁵⁹

1) Visual rehabilitation:

a) Optical correction:

Spectacle lenses: The optical correction of myopia is accomplished by interposing a concave lens between cornea and the far point of the eye (Fig. 6). Myopia should never be overcorrected. This can be done with duochrome test, which gives an extremely precise end point when the red objects are seen slightly more clearly than the green.

Fig. 7: Refraction in a myopic eye corrected with concave lens.

But motility disorders can vary the final prescriptions to some extent. A young symptomatic myopia with moderate esophoria may function better with some degree of under correction.

Adolescent may not accept full correction for near work, because they are accustomed to read without exercising accommodation, he may indeed be more comfortable without spectacles or with weaker lenses. It should be impressed upon him that in the matter of near work, they are not intended to improve his vision but to allow him to use his eyes in their normal relationship.

In adults, on the other hand, in whom visual habits have become stabilized, such a care is unnecessary and the constant use of spectacles need not be insisted upon; moreover, in the absence of previous correction it will frequently be found that the ciliary muscle is not equal to the unaccustomed task of accommodating efficiently, so that a lens of slightly lower power may be prescribed with comfort for reading.

In the lower degrees of myopia, the necessity for regular supervision once the condition is static is questionable; in general low myopes change little after the end of adolescent and they may be confidently advised to return for further examination only if their spectacle frames or lenses become physically damaged or if they notice any deterioration in their corrected vision. They should be reassured that the latter event is unlikely in any event before the age of 40 yrs. Above the age of 40 yrs, when accommodation fails physiologically, weaker lenses for near work are advisable or the spectacles can be removed.

In the higher degree of myopia, full correction can rarely be tolerated largely because the images formed by strong concave lenses are diminished and very bright and clear, and the patient, accustomed to interpret hazy diffusion circles, is intolerant of them. A compromise must therefore be adopted, and while an attempt is made to reduce the correction as little as is compatible with comfort for binocular vision, lenses are prescribed with which greatest visual acuity is obtained without distress. The amount which has to be deducted usually varies from 1 to 3D, but in the highest grades spectacles even weaker than these will be found necessary. In these cases contact lenses may be of value if they are easily tolerated.

Optical correction of pathological myopia is the same as that of simple myopia. In higher degree of myopia, full correction is less tolerated. Vertex distance

of new lenses should always be noted on the prescription. Small frames can be preferred to reduce the weight. Thick edge can be camouflaged by coloring the edges of the lens as that of the frame. Plastic lenses are better. In cases where in degenerative changes have taken place in the macular area telescopic spectacles are of value.

If the spectacles are not worn constantly, especially in high myopia, the requisite amount of convergence for near work may be impossible. The effort to converge is thus abandoned so that reading and other near work may become unocular and the disused eye may become divergent.^{51,60}

Contact lenses:

These offer both optical and cosmetic advantages over spectacles. Both hard and soft contact lenses can be used in myopic patients. Rigid contact lenses require less care and produce better results and can correct substantial degree of astigmatism. Soft contact lenses are easy to wear and have better patient compliance. But they require more care and maintenance. Low myopia being perhaps the most widespread indication for their use. They offer dramatically improved appearance and enhance the visual acuity in high myopes.

Advantages of contact lenses over spectacles:

Optical:

- Near normal image size.
- Wider field of vision
- Elimination of distortions and aberrations associated with spectacles
- Minimal prismatic experience.
- Better adaptation in anisometropics.

Cosmetic:

- Spectacles can be avoided
- Appearance of small eye behind the spectacles is overcome.
- Large and attractive globe is seen.
-

Disadvantages of contact lenses:

Greater effort of accommodation and convergence is required; this may be of no consequences in young myopes, but is important for presbyopic patients in whom difficulties in near vision may be precipitated.

Moderate degrees of myopia are ideally corrected by corneal lenses, and a variety of fitting techniques and designs are available. The choice of which depends upon the personal fancy and experience of the individual practitioner.

In the higher degree, the optical advantage of the corneal contact lenses are correspondingly increased, but problems arise in their fitting i.e. lenses are heavy and every effort is made to fashion them to be as thin as possible; a central thickness of 0.1 mm or slightly less is about the minimum that can be produced consistent with mechanical stability.

Low vision aids:

In case of high myopia, the most useful low vision aid for distance is the telescopic lens. The disadvantages of these are their weight and restriction of peripheral field. New models feature a small telescopic lens inserted eccentrically to the normal visual axis, and can be brought into play only when patient needs to discern greater details. These lenses give advantages of telescopic magnification without the restriction of visual field.

b) Surgical correction of myopia:

Surgery to correct myopia has become very popular and it should be performed after the error has stabilized preferably after 20yrs of age.^{35,48} Refractive surgery is now the second most common procedure in Singapore after cataract surgery.⁶¹ Various techniques in use are described below:

1. Radial keratotomy: (RK)

It refers to making deep (90% of corneal thickness) radial incisions in the peripheral part of cornea leaving the central 4mm optical zone (Fig. 7A &B). These incisions on healing; flatten the central cornea thereby reducing its refractive power. This gives very good correction in low to moderate myopia (2-6D).

Fig. 8: Radial keratotomy

A) Configurations of radial incisions B) Depth of incision.

Disadvantages Cornea is weakened, so chances of globe rupture following trauma are more after RK than after PRK. This point is particularly important for patients who are at high risk of blunt trauma e.g. sports persons, athletes and military personnel.

- Rarely uneven healing may lead to irregular astigmatism.
- Patients may feel glare at night.
- Perforation and infection.

Because of its disadvantages. RK is not recommended presently.

2. Photorefractive keratectomy (PRK):

In this technique, to correct myopia a central optical zone of anterior corneal stroma is photoablated using excimer laser (Fig. 8 A & B). Like RK, the PRK also gives very good correction for -2 to -6D of myopia.

Fig 9: PRK for myopia as seen A) from front B) in cross section

Disadvantages:

- Postoperative recovery is slow; healing of the epithelial defect may delay return of good vision and patient may experience pain or discomfort for several weeks.
- There might be some residual corneal haze in the centre affecting vision.
- PRK is more expensive than RK.
- Loss of contrast sensitivity.

Because of these disadvantages, PRK is not recommended presently.

3. Laser in-situ keratomileusis (LASIK):

In this technique, first a flap of 130-160 micron thickness of anterior corneal tissue is raised. After creating a corneal flap, midstromal tissue is ablated directly with an excimer laser beam, ultimately flattening the cornea (Fig. 9 A, B & C). Currently this procedure is being considered the refractive surgery of choice for myopia of upto -12D.^{48, 62}

Fig. 10: LASIK A) Microkeratome cut, B) Laser photoablation with flap lifted, C) Flap repositioned. Thinner, flatter cornea.

Patient selection criteria are:

- Patients above 18 years of age,
- Stable refraction for 12 months (A change of refraction within ± 0.5 over one year is considered stable).
- Motivated patient.
- Absence of corneal pathology, presence of ectasia or any other corneal pathology and a corneal thickness less than 450 microns is an absolute contraindication for LASIK.

Advances in LASIK:

Recently many advances have been made in LASIK surgery.

A. Customized (C) LASIK:

C-LASIK is based on wave front technology. This technique, in addition to spherical and cylindrical correction, also corrects the aberrations present in the eye and gives vision beyond 6/6 i.e. 6/5 or 6/4.

B. Epi-(E) LASIK:

In this technique, instead of corneal stromal flap only the epithelial sheet is separated mechanically with the use of customized device (Epiedge Epikeratome). Being an advanced surface ablation procedure, it is devoid of complications related to corneal stromal flap.

Advantages of LASIK:

- Minimal or no postoperative pain.
- Recovery of vision is very early as compared to PRK.
- No risk of perforation during surgery and later rupture of globe due to trauma unlike RK.
- No residual haze unlike PRK where sub epithelial scarring may occur
- LASIK is effective in correcting myopia of -12D.

Disadvantages of LASIK:

- LASIK is more expensive.
- It requires greater surgical skill than RK and PRK.
- Flap related complications like
 - Intra-operative flap amputation.
 - Wrinkling of the flap on repositioning.
 - Postoperative flap dislocation/subluxation.

- Epithelization of flap-bed interface.
- Irregular astigmatism.

4. Clear lens extraction (Fucala's operation):

This has been advocated for myopia of -16 to -18D, especially in unilateral cases. Recently clear lens extraction with intraocular lens implantation of appropriate power is being recommended as the refractive surgery for myopia of more than 12D.

Disadvantages:

- Retinal detachment
- Endophthalmitis.

5. PHAKIC IOL (intraocular contact lens implantation):

Is considered for correction of myopia of >12D. In this technique, a special type of intraocular lens is implanted in the anterior chamber or posterior chamber anterior to the natural crystalline lens.

Complications:

- Endophthalmitis.
- Cataract.

6. Intracorneal ring (ICR) implantation or INTACS:

ICR implantation into the peripheral cornea at approximately 2/3rd stromal depth is being considered. It results in a vaulting effect that flattens the central cornea, decreasing myopia. The ICR procedure has the advantage of being reversible. It corrects myopia upto-6.0 Dioptres.

Disadvantages being unpredictable results and keratitis.

7. Orthokeratology:

A nonsurgical reversible method of moulding the cornea with overnight wear unique rigid gas permeable contact lenses is also being considered for correction of myopia upto -5D. It can be used even in patients below 18 years of age.

8. Epikeratophakia:

This technique was first developed by Kaufman in 1979. This technique involves removing the recipient epithelium after making a little peripheral trephine mark of defect in Bowman's membrane. A freeze-dried or lyophilized piece of stroma is placed on the surface of the recipient cornea and sutured into stroma. The epithelium grows over the Bowman's membrane to cover the new surface and in effect, a living contact lens has been applied.

2) Prevention of Myopic Progression:

a) General supportive measures: Like balanced diet, with abundant amount of proteins, vitamins especially vitamin C and calcium. Regular exercises and outdoor games are advised.

b) Modification of ocular use:

Patients are occupationally rehabilitated to prevent excessive close work, ocular hygienic measures like avoiding close work, reading under well illuminated conditions in proper posture. The clarity of print should be suitably supervised and undue ocular fatigue should be avoided. The amount of work should be adjusted to the general physical and mental development of the child rather than to the degree of myopia, and only if the child appears strained under the forced or competitive stress of school life which is sometimes considerable should be withdrawn from school or his study cut down.

c) Contact lenses:

Rigid contact lenses have been used in several clinical trials, as it is postulated that these lenses retard myopia progression by causing corneal flattening.⁵⁰

Effect of contact lenses over the arrest of progression of myopia:

There is a difference of opinion as regards to it. Some says it arrests the progression of myopia and some says myopia may progress to its destiny in spite of wearing and still some other are of the opinion that myopia may increase when the use of contact lenses have been discontinued.

As per as the management of simple myopia is concerned whether the patient be an adult or child, the extent to which spectacles are worn, the amount of near work done, peculiarities of diet or the administration of drugs are of small moment provided that hygienic conditions are good, over strain is avoided and the general standards of health and development are maintained.

Myopia control:

Attempts to slow the progression of myopia are considered as myopic control. There are presently a number of options for myopia prevention and control. That include^{50, 63-69}:

- Bifocals.
- Rigid contact lens
- Topical eye drops like atropine
- Agents that lower intraocular pressure.
- Optical lenses
- Biofeedback methods.

However the effectiveness of some of these methods is questionable, and there is inadequate scientific evidence for implementation in a population setting.

Many clinical trials lacked randomization, had high dropout rates or failed to account for confounding. On the other hand it is difficult to prescribe interventions to reduce exposure to either intermediate or distal factors like education, near work and living conditions.

3) Prophylaxis:

Prophylactic eugenic measures should be adopted. There need be no restraint on marriage and procreation among simple myopes; but a parent with degenerative myopia should be warned that any offspring will be liable to the same disability according to the laws of Mendelian inheritance. Two highly myopic parents with degenerative changes should never-from the medical point of view-have children. The children of such parents should be closely supervised from their earliest years and if an increase in refractivity appears to evolve more rapidly than would normally be expected, they should be treated as if they were myopes.^{12,51}

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Method of collection of data:

This is a cross sectional and time bound study in which simple random sampling among schools in Bijapur city was done. All the children between 7-15 yrs of age in the selected schools were examined for visual impairment from October 2012 to March 2014.

The purpose and method of examination of students were explained to the head of the schools concerned. A large room with plugging system and electricity supply was selected. With the help of the respective class teachers each class was subjected to visual acuity tests, student by student. After obtaining consent from parents students were subjected for vision screening. The students whose visual acuity was observed to be 6/9 or less was again subjected to visual acuity test in B.L.D.E Medical College. The list of such students was given to the class teachers and school head mistress / master. Their parents were informed by the school authority to take the students to outpatient department of ophthalmology, Shri B.M.Patil Medical College & Research Centre, Bijapur on a particular day. The students were subjected to torch light examination, retinoscopy and fundus examination. Refractive errors and other ailments of the eye were treated wherever necessary. The condition and prognosis were explained to the parents. Data was recorded and analyzed.

Source of data and sampling procedure:

Block education officer, Bijapur was approached with the requisition for the permission of collection of data. It was decided to have a simple random sampling. The list of schools in Bijapur city was obtained; primary schools and high schools were numbered separately. The chits bearing the numbers were rolled and put in two

boxes separately- One for the government schools and the other for the private schools. The chits were drawn like the lottery method.

The schools selected were -

Government schools:

- 1) Govt. Kannada Boys Model Primary School, No 5, B.L.D.E Road.
- 2) Govt. Kannada Girls Higher Primary School, No 5, Near Amir Talkies.
- 3) Govt. Kannada High School, No 24, Jalnagar.
- 4) Govt. Kannada Higher Primary School, No 37, Mallikarjun Nagar

Private Schools:

1. Prerna Public School, Bhutnal.
2. Saraswathi Primary & High School,

These above-mentioned schools were instructed by the Block education officer, Bijapur to co-operate in the ophthalmic examination of the students and separate requisition letters to each school from Professor and Head of the department were also given.

Sample Size:²⁹

Formula

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times p \times q}{l^2}$$

Where n = Sample size

p = Prevalence of positive character i.e. Myopia

q = 100-p

l = Allowable error taken to be 1%

Therefore, a minimum of 1252 cases will be included in the study. As it is time bound study, we got more number of school children during our study period. The size of sample taken was 1374 children.

Statistical analysis:

Data will be analysed

- Using Mean \pm Standard deviation data will be presented.
- Using statistical tests like t-test, χ^2 test etc.

According to modified BG Prasad's⁷⁰ classification, children were classified into different social classes as follows

Table 3: Socio-economic status modified BG Prasad's classification.

Social class	Per capita monthly income limits (Rs) modified B G Prasad's classification
I-Upper class	≥ 5156
II-High	2578-5155
III-Upper middle	1547-2577
IV-Lower middle	773-1546
V- Poor	< 773

Social class number was given to them accordingly and data was analyzed.

Inclusion criteria:

School children between 7 –15 years of age of either sex in the selected school. School children in the selected schools of Bijapur city with myopia.

Exclusion criteria:

Visual impairment due to

Refractive errors other than myopia.

Corneal opacities

Lens opacities.

Retinal diseases.

Drop outs.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Total No. of children screened 1374

Total No. of Schools Visited 6

Table 4: The prevalence of myopia among students of various schools.

Sl. No.	School Name	Boys	Girls	Total	No. of myopics.
1	Govt. Kannada Boys Model Primary School, No 5	189	0	189	12
2	Govt. Kannada Girls Higher Primary School, No 5	0	238	238	12
3	Govt. Kannada High School, No 24	52	69	121	12
4	Govt. Kannada Higher Primary School, No 37	90	109	199	12
5	Prerna Public School	228	179	407	44
6	Sarswathi Primary & High School.	141	79	220	21
Total		700	674	1374	113

In our study out of 1374, there were 700 boys (7.0%) and 674 (9.5%) girls. Among them 113 (8.2%) were myopics. From government schools we had 747 students. Out of which 331 (44.3%) were boys and 416 (55.7%) were girls. Total number of myopic students from government schools was 48 (6.4%). From private schools we had 627 students. Out of which 369 (58.9%) were boys and 258 (41.1%) were girls. Total number of myopic students from private schools was 65 (10.4%). It was found that prevalence of myopia found to be more in private school 65 (4.7%) students than government schools 48 (3.5%) students.

Chart 1: The prevalence of myopia among students of various schools.

Table 5: Prevalence of myopia.

Total no of children	Total myopes	Prevalence (%)
1374	113	8.2

In our study total 1374 students were screened among them 113 students had myopia. Prevalence of myopia was found to be 8.2%.

Chart 2: Prevalence of myopia.

Table 6: Prevalence of myopia in different genders.

Sex	Total no	No. of Myopics	Prevalence (%)	<i>p</i> -value
Boys	700	49	7.0	<0.848
Girls	674	64	9.5	

$$\chi^2 = 0.805, p < 0.848$$

Among 113 children 64 (9.5%) were girls and 49 (7%) were boys. In this study prevalence of myopia was found to be more amongst girls than boys.

Using chi-square test, $\chi^2 = 0.805, p < 0.848$, it is not significant.

Chart 3: Prevalence of myopia in different genders.

Table 7: Class wise prevalence (approximately equaling age).

Class	No. of student	No. of cases	prevalence
II	147	7	4.7
III	177	11	6.2
IV	156	11	7.1
V	173	13	7.5
VI	162	15	9.3
VII	235	22	9.4
VIII	125	12	9.6
IX	112	12	10.7
X	87	10	11.5
Total	1374	113	8.2

The least prevalence of myopia was found in II class (4.7%) and highest prevalence was found in X class (11.5%). General observation was that the prevalence of myopia was more in older students.

Chart 4: Class wise prevalence.

Table 8: Visual acuity before correction.

VA	No. of eyes	Percentage (%)
6/9	40	18.1
6/12	33	14.9
6/18	46	20.8
6/24	45	20.4
6/36	22	9.9
6/60	17	7.7
CF3mtr	03	1.4
CF4mtr	10	4.5
CF5mtr	05	2.3
Total	221	100

In our study total of 226 eyes of 113 students 5 eyes had no refractive error. So, considering 221 myopic eyes 46 (20.8%) eyes had visual acuity 6/18 at least in one eye before correction was found to be high and 3 (1.4%) eyes had visual acuity CF 3mtr at least in one eye before correction was found to be lowest.

Chart 5: Visual acuity before correction.

Table 9: Visual acuity after correction.

Corrected VA	No. of eyes	Percentage (%)
6/6	213	96.4
6/9	06	2.7
6/12	02	0.9
Total	221	100

After optical correction, the corrected visual acuity was almost near normal in most of the eyes 213 (96.4%). 6 (2.7%) eyes had distant vision (6/9) and 2 (0.9%) eyes had distant vision (6/12) even after correction. This could be due to possible amblyopia.

Chart 6: visual acuity after correction.

Table 10: Unilateral & bilateral myopia.

Laterality	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Unilateral	05	4.50
Bilateral	108	95.5
Total	113	100

In our study out of 113 cases, 108 (95.5%) students had bilateral myopia. Only 5 (4.5%) students had unilateral myopia.

Chart 7: Unilateral & bilateral myopia.

Table 11: Degree of myopia.

Degree of myopia	< -3.0D (mild)	-3.0 to -6.0D (moderate)	> -6.0D (high)	Total
No. of eyes	174	39	08	221
percentage	78.7	17.6	3.61	100.0

In total of 221 eyes, 174 (78.7%) eyes had a refractive error of less than -3.0 D. 39 (17.6%) eyes were between -3 to -6 D myopia and 8 (3.61%) eyes were >-6 D myopia.

Chart 8: Degree of myopia.

Table 12: Mean, Standard deviation of degree of myopia.

	Mean	Standard deviation
Mild	-1.14	0.717
Moderate	-3.76	0.774
Severe	-8.18	1.607

Table 13: Simple myopia and Pathological myopia.

	Simple Myopia	Pathological Myopia
Cases	155	14
Percentage (%)	70.1	6.3

In total of 221 eyes, 155 (70.1%) eyes had Simple myopic refractive error and 14 (6.3%) eyes had Pathological myopia. Overall simple myopia was found to be more than pathological myopia.

Chart 9: Simple myopia and Pathological myopia.

Table 14: Types of Astigmatism.

Types of Astigmatism	Simple Myopic Astigmatism	Compound Myopic Astigmatism
Cases	21	45
Percentage	9.5%	20.4%

In total of 221 eyes, 21 (9.5%) eyes had Simple myopic astigmatic refractive error and 45 (20.4%) eyes had Compound myopic astigmatic refractive error.

Chart 10: Types of Astigmatism.

Myopia and Socio-economic status:

Table 15: Prevalence of myopia with reference to various socio-economic classes in government and private schools.

Socio-economic class	Cases		Total	p-value
	Govt	Private		
Upper class	00	49	431	<0.0001*
High	00	15	196	
Upper middle	20	01	312	
Lower middle	28	00	435	
Total	48	65	1374	

$\chi^2=109.1, p < 0.0001$

In our study out of 113 cases, the prevalence of myopia was more among children belonging to Upper High socio-economic status (43.4%) than children belonging to Lower Middle socio-economic status (24.8%).

Using chi-square test, $\chi^2 = 109.1, p < 0.0001$, it is statistically significant in Upper High socio-economic status had increased prevalence.

Chart 11: Prevalence of myopia with reference to various socio-economic classes in government and private schools.

Table 16: Myopia and near work.

Near work	Myopia cases					
	Govt school			Private school		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
1-2	12	12	24	3	4	07
3-4	8	7	15	10	14	24
5-6	2	2	04	9	16	25
7-8	00	5	05	5	4	09
9-10	00	00	00	00	00	00
Total	22	26	48	27	38	65

$\chi^2 = 25.3, p < 0.0001$

In our study out of the 113 myopic patients of government and private schools there was a highly significant association between myopia and near work. Students of private schools were spending significantly more time than the students of government schools in the near-work activities.

Using chi-square test, $\chi^2 = 25.3, p < 0.0001$, it is statistically significant. It shows that there is statistically significant association between prevalence of myopia and amount of hours spent for near work.

Chart 12: Myopia according to near work.

Table 17: School wise distribution of ocular condition.

		SPK	VKC	B	CX	BS	TOTAL
01	Govt. Kannada Boys Model Primary School, No 5	01	01	01	2	00	5
02	Govt. Kannada Girls Higher Primary School, No 5	00	01	03	00	01	5
03	Govt. Kannada High School, No 24	00	01	01	01	00	03
04	Govt. Kannada Higher Primary School, No 37	00	00	03	01	01	05
05	Prerna Public School	02	02	02	00	00	06
06	Saraswati Primary & High School.	01	01	01	01	00	04
	Total	04	6	11	5	02	28

(SPK= superficial punctate keratitis, VKC= vernal keratoconjunctivitis, B= blepharitis, CX= conjunctival xerosis, BS= bitot's spot)

In our study out of 1374 children examined, 28 (2.03%) children had some ocular manifestations. Among all types of ocular condition, it was found that maximum numbers of cases were Blepharitis. Among all schools, it was found that prevalence of Blepharitis was high in Govt. Kannada Girls Higher Primary School and Govt. Kannada Higher Primary School.

Table no. 18: Distribution of students with myopia cases with ocular conditions.

Schools		Ocular conditions				
		SPK	VKC	B	CX	TOTAL
01	Govt. Kannada Boys Model Primary School, No 5	01	01	00	00	02
02	Govt. Kannada Girls Higher Primary School, No 5	00	01	02	00	03
03	Govt. Kannada High School, No 24	00	01	00	00	01
04	Govt. Kannada Higher Primary School, No 37	00	00	01	01	02
05	Perna Public School	02	02	01	00	05
06	Saraswati Primary & High School.	01	01	01	00	03
Total		04	06	05	01	16

(SPK= superficial punctate keratitis, VKC= vernal keratoconjunctivitis, B= blepharitis, CX= conjunctival xerosis, BS= bitot's spot)

In our study out of 113 myopic children, 16 (14.2%) children had ocular manifestations. Among all types of ocular condition, it was found that maximum numbers of cases were vernal keratoconjunctivitis.

Table 19: Fundus changes in Pathological Myopia.

Fundus	Frequency	Percentage
DL,TC	05	35.7
TC	02	14.3
DL,TC,ST	03	21.4
DL,AC,ST,DG	01	7.1
DL,AC,ST	01	7.1
DL,TC,ST,DG	02	14.3
TOTAL	14	100.0

(DL= large disc, TC temporal crescent, ST= super traction, AC= annular crescent, DG= degenerative changes)

in our study out of 221 eyes, 14 (6.3%) eyes found to have pathological myopia changes. among them 5 (35.7%) eyes had large disc with temporal crescent, 2 (14.3%) eyes had only temporal crescent. 3 (21.4%) eyes had large disc, temporal crescent and super traction. 1 (7.1%) eye had large disc, annular crescent, super traction and degenerative changes. 1 (7.1%) eye had large disc, annular crescent and super traction. 2 (14.3%) eyes had large disc, temporal crescent, super traction and degenerative changes.

Chart 13: Fundus changes in Pathological Myopia.

DISCUSSION

A cross sectional and time bound study was done between October 2012 to March 2014 in school going children between 7-15 yrs of age in Bijapur city.

Prevalence of Myopia:

In our study, out of the 1374 students examined 266 students (8.2%) were found to have myopia in at least one eye of the students had myopia.

When compared to other studies by different authors with respect to different parameters are shown as follows.

Table 20: Comparison with different studies.

Study	Country	Sample size	Age(yrs)	Myopia definition	Cycloplegic refraction	Prevalence (%)
Lithander J. ⁷¹	Oman	6292	6	$\leq -1.0D$	Yes	0.56
			12	$\leq -1.0D$		5.16
Zhao J. ⁷²	China	6134	5-15	$\leq -0.5D$	Yes	14.9
Maul E. ⁷³	Chile	5303	5-15	$\leq -0.5D$	Yes	7.3
Dandona R. ⁷⁴	India (rural)	4074	7-15	$\leq -0.5D$	Yes	4.1
Murthy GV ²⁶	India (Urban)	6447	5-15	$\leq -0.5D$	Yes	7.4
Naidoo KS. ⁷⁵	South Africa	4890	5-15	$\leq -0.5D$	Yes	4.0
Lin ¹⁷	Taiwan	11178	6-18	≤ -0.25	Yes	12% at 6yrs, 56% at 12yrs
Ghosh S ²⁹	India	2570	6-14	VA < 6/6	Yes	11.9
Kalikivayi. V. ²⁵	India	4029	3-18	$\leq -0.5D$	No	8.6
Present study	India	1374	7-15	VA 6/9	Yes	8.2

The prevalence of myopia in the above table are almost comparable to our present study especially the studies of Indian origin.

Sex distribution:

In our study, the prevalence of myopia in girls was (9.5%) found to be more than that of the boys (7.0%). A study conducted on Greek students between 15-18 yrs in 1998 by Mavracanas TA et al.⁵² Showed myopia to be more common in females (46%) than in males (29.7%). Our study also shows myopia prevalence is more for females (9.5%) than for males (7.0%).

Table 21: Comparison with other studies as follows:

	Boys	Girls
Mavracanas TA et al. ⁷⁶	29.7%	46%
Ahmed I et al. ⁷⁷	3.6%	5.54%
Ghosh S et al. ²⁹	48%	52%
Present study	7%	9.5%

Class wise prevalence (approximately equaling age):

In our study of 1374 students, it was found that students in higher standards had higher prevalence of myopia than students of lower standard. It was found that X class had 11.5% of prevalence and II class had lowest prevalence 4.7%.

Study by Murthy GV et al.²⁶ shown prevalence of myopia correlated positively with older age, which is also comparable to our present study.

Danoda R et al.⁷⁴ studied children between 7-15 years at Andhra Pradesh, India, and found the prevalence of myopia to be 4.1% and was significantly higher in children with older age; this was also comparable to our present study.

Table 22: Class wise comparison with different studies as follows:

	Class II	Class IX
Murthy GV et al. ²⁶	3.13%	10.8%
Danoda R et al. ⁷⁴	2.80%	6.72%
Naidoo KS et al. ⁷⁵	2.5%	9.6%
Present Study	4.7%	11.5%

Vision improvement:

In present study visual acuity less than 6/6 at least in one eye was present in 221 eyes. Out of these 221 eyes, visual acuity improved to 6/6 with correction in 213 eyes (96.4%) which is comparable to our study. Only 8 eyes (3.6%) of 221 eyes did not improve to 6/6 with correction due to possibly developed amblyopia.

Study by Ghosh S et al.²⁹ shown visual acuity less than 6/6 at least in one eye was present in 754 eyes. Out of these 754 eyes, visual acuity improved with correction in 712 eyes (94.4%).

Table 23: vision improvement compare with other study.

	No of Eyes	No of Eyes with improved vision	Percentage (%)
Ghosh S et al. ²⁹	754	712	94.4%
Present Study	221	213	96.4%

Types of Myopia:

In our study, out of 226 eyes 155 (71.1%) eyes had simple myopia, 21 (9.5%) eyes had simple myopic astigmatism and 45 (20.4%) eyes had compound myopic

astigmatism. Out of 113 cases, only 5 cases had unilateral myopia, rest of the cases had bilateral myopia.

Study by Ghosh S et al.²⁹ shown out of 5139 eyes 370 (7.2%) eyes had simple myopia, 208 (4.05%) eyes had simple myopic astigmatism and 10 (0.2%) eyes had compound myopic astigmatism.

Overall, simple myopia cases were found to be more than simple and compound myopic astigmatism in our study when comparing to the above study.

Myopia and socio-economic status:

In our study, the prevalence of myopia was more among children belonging to Upper High socio-economic status (43.4%) than children belonging to Lower Middle socio-economic status (24.8%) with p value < 0.0001 , which is statistically significant in Upper High socio-economic status.

A study done by Chandra DB et al.⁷⁸ has shown the myopia prevalence is more among the children belonging to good socio-economic status. And myopia was unilateral in 6% of cases, which are comparable to our present study.

Sperduto RD et al.⁴³ in his study found prevalence rates of myopia were significantly lower for men than for women for all age, and myopia prevalence rose with family income which is also comparable to our present study.

Myopia and near work:

In present study, 113 myopic patients of government and private schools there was a highly significant association between myopia and near work. It suggests that students of private schools were spending significantly more time than the students of government schools in the near-work activities.

A comparative study by Ip JM et al.⁷⁹ of 2353 patients between government and private schools, reported that girls were spending significantly more time than did

the boys in the near-work activities of completing homework, reading books and using a computer. The study also showed that the prevalence of myopia in girl was (14.1%) with a greater tendency of myopic refraction and greater time spent in near-work activities.

In other study by Saw SM et al.⁸⁰ also showed increased near-work which contributed to prevalence of myopia.

Association of ocular condition:

Of 1374 children examined, 7 (0.50%) had clinical signs of xerophthalmia. The overall prevalence of VAD was found to be 0.50% which is comparable to (0.36%) and (1.00%) reported by Nepal DP et al.¹¹ and Singh P et al.⁸¹ respectively. Most of them exhibited conjunctival xerosis 5 children (85.7%) and 2 (28.6%) had bitot's spot. None had any corneal xerosis, corneal scar, Keratomalacia or fundal xerosis. According to prevalence of bitot's spot in various states in India, Karnataka was found to have (0.7%) which is (0.15%) comparable to our study. The prevalence of VAD was higher among the children belonging to government schools (6 students) than private schools (1 student). Similar observation was found in the study done by Khan S et al.⁸² this could be attributed to fact that children from poor socio-economic status live in unsanitary surroundings have poor access to basic health care and unhealthy dietary pattern contributing to poor nutritional status.

VKC remained the second most common cause (5 children, 0.4%) of ocular morbidity in children. Higher prevalence (4-17.23%) of vernal keratoconjunctivitis has been reported by various other studies.^{83,84} Though VKC rarely does lead to blindness, but it remains a leading cause of school absenteeism due to its discomfort, chronicity, and recurrence.

In this study, the prevalence of squamous blepharitis was found to be 0.80% which was comparable to the prevalence found in other studies i.e. Trivedi et al.⁸⁵ observed 0.93%, Sherpa D et al.⁸⁶ observed 0.85%.

Pathological Myopia:

In a study conducted by Wong TY, Loon SC, Saw SM et al.⁸⁷ shows significant proportion of Asian adults have high myopia, and may therefore be at risk of potentially blinding conditions such as myopic degeneration. While the prevalence of high myopia is less than 2% in most western studies. In our present study, the proportion of high myopia is 3.5%, which is slightly higher than western studies.

CONCLUSION

Observations and results showed that simple myopia is more common in school going children. Majority of the cases were detected only during the screening of the students. So, majority of them go unnoticed, making more and more students visually handicapped.

But with the co-operation of the teachers, school authorities and health workers at primary health center level, affected can be treated with proper optical correction, thereby reducing morbidity due to myopia.

Thus an early diagnosis and visual rehabilitation of myopic students can be achieved by periodic eye examination at regular intervals by school teachers and basic health workers and educating them regarding optical correction of myopia thereby preventing the development of amblyopia will definitely reduce the burden of morbidity due to myopia.

SUMMARY

In our present study, 1374 school children between 7 to 15 yrs in Bijapur city were screened. The prevalence of myopia was found to be 8.2% and majority of the myopes were girls.

The highest prevalence was found in students studying in 10th class. Majority of the students had visual acuity better than 6/12.

After optical correction the corrected visual acuity was almost near normal in most of the eyes.

6 (2.7%) eyes had distant vision (6/9) and 2 (0.9%) eyes had distant vision (6/12) even after correction.

Majority of the students had bilateral myopia. Most of the eyes had a refractive error of less than – 3.0 D. Only 3.61% of eyes had an error of –6.0D and above. Most of the eyes of these students had simple myopia and corrected with spherical lenses alone.

The prevalence of myopia was more among children belonging to higher socio economic status and private school compare with government schools. Majority of the myopic children examined did not complain of any symptoms.

In our study factors like age, sex and socio-economic status, near work have got some bearing on the prevalence of myopia which may need further proof. Though we can not comment their influence in any precise way, by analysis of data, at least the direction of some of these influences sometimes can be taken into account.

Large numbers of school going children are unaware of their refractive errors. Hence periodical check up of school going children to detect in early stages is helpful. All the defective cases should be registered and followed up regularly. The parents

and teachers should be made aware of the importance of the early detection and correction of myopia in order to prevent amblyopia and squint.

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ANNEXURE

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR-586 103
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this college met on 18-10-2012 at 03-30 pm to scrutinize the Synopsis of Postgraduate Students of this college from Ethical Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected & revised version synopsis of the Thesis has been accorded Ethical Clearance.

Title "Study of prevalence of myopia in school going children in Bijapur city"
— x — x —

Name of P.G. student Dr. Darshankumar U. Karsara
Ophthalmology

Name of Guide/Co-investigator Dr. Sunil G. Borade
post. ophthalmology

DR. TEJASWINI VALLABHA
CHAIRMAN
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE
BLDEU'S, SHRI.B.M.PATIL
MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR.

Following documents were placed before E.C. for Scrutinization

- 1) Copy of Synopsis/Research project.
- 2) Copy of informed consent form
- 3) Any other relevant documents.

ANNEXURE

SAMPLE INFORMED CONSENT FORM

**B.L.D.E.U.'s SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR – 586103, KARNATAKA**

TITLE OF THE PROJECT: “STUDY OF PREVALENCE OF
MYOPIA IN SCHOOL GOING
CHILDREN IN BIJAPUR CITY”

PRINCIPAL INVESTEGATOR: **DR. DARSHANKUMAR U. KANSARA**
Department of Ophthalmology
Email: kdarshan83@yahoo.com

PG GUIDE: **DR. SUNIL G. BIRADAR. M.S.**
Professor of Ophthalmology
B.L.D.E.U's Shri B.M. Patil
Medical College Hospital & Research
Centre, Sholapur Road,
Bijapur – 586103

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

This study is to determine the prevalence of myopia in school going children in Biapur city and to treat it wherever necessary.

I/ My ward have been explained about the reason for doing this study and selecting me/my ward as a subject for this study. I /My ward have also been given free choice for either being included or not in the study.

PROCEDURE:

I/my ward will be subjected to detailed history and systemic and ocular examination. I/My ward will then performing visual acuity testing, cycloplegic refraction and give correction for refractive error.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I/My ward understand that I/my ward have to undergo a complete ocular and systemic examination as required. I/My ward may have blurring of vision for a few hours as a result of pharmacological pupil dilatation for detailed fundus evaluation. I /My ward may have to undergo the various tests required and to expect a time delay for all the various test reports to come.

BENEFITS:

I/ My ward understand that I/my wards participation in this study will help this study is to determine prevalence of myopia of school going children in urban area and to treat it wherever is necessary.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I/My ward understand that medical information produced by this study will become a part of this Hospital records and will be subjected to the confidentiality and privacy regulation of this hospital. Information of a sensitive, personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate secure location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no names will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or

video tapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photograph and videotapes and hear audiotapes before giving this permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I/My ward understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. **Dr. DARSHANKUMAR U. KANSARA** is available to answer my questions or concerns. I/ My ward understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of this study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during this study, or later, I/ My ward wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me.

And that a copy of this consent form will be given to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWL OF PARTICIPATION:

I/My ward understand that my participation is voluntary and I/My ward may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital.

I also understand that **Dr. DARSHANKUMAR U. KANSARA** will terminate my participation in this study at any time after she has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or therapist, if this is appropriate.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I/ My ward understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me I/my ward, resulting directly to my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, then medical treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation will be provided.

I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study, I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of this research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits, to the best of my ability in patient's own language.

Date:

DR. SUNIL G. BIRADAR

(Guide)

Dr .DARSHANKUMAR U.KANSARA

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I confirm that **Dr. DARSHANKUMAR U. KANSARA** has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I have been explained all the above in detail, in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Participant)

Date:

(Witness to above signature)

Date:

PARENTS CONSENT STATEMENT:

I confirm that **Dr. DARSHANKUMAR U. KANSARA** has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that my child will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that my child may experience, in my own language.

I have been explained all the above contents in detail, in my own vernacular language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Parents)

Date:

(Witness to above signature)

Date:

ANNEXURE

CASE SHEET PROFORMA

Name: _____ Date: _____
Age/Sex: _____ O.P.No./I.P.NO _____
Education/Class: _____ Rural/Urban: _____
DOB: _____
Address: _____
Socio Economic Status: _____
Hobbies: _____
Hours of near work: _____
History of presenting complaints: _____

H/O Dimness of Vision	+/-
H/O Headache	+/-
H/O Eye strain	+/-
H/O Diplopia	+/-
H/O Watering	+/-
H/O Itching	+/-
H/O Recurrent stye	+/-

Other History

Past History	:	History of using glasses	
Personal History	:	Diet =	Bowel/Bladder
		Appetite	Slee

Treatment History: History of treatment taken for ocular diseases
or other diseases

History of allergic reactions to drugs.

History of blood transfusion.

Family history : Number of family members

History of similar complaints

General Examination: Patient is _____year old_____ Built
&_____ Weight

Vital Data : Pulse Temperature
BP RR

Ocular Examination:

Head Posture

Facial symmetry

Visual axis

Right eye

Left eye

Extra ocular movements:

Visual acuity: Distance: Unaided:

Pinhole:

Near vision:

Adnexa

Conjunctiva

Cornea

AC

Iris

Pupil

Lens

Fundus

Retinoscopy: Dry:

cycloplegic

IOP

A-scan

B-scan

Diagnosis:

Subjective reading:

Fig 11: Torchlight Examination.

Fig 12: Fundus Examination.

Fig 13: Slitlamp Examination.

Fig 14: Retinoscopy.

Fig 15: Screening at government school.

KEY TO MASTER CHART

N	-	Normal
NA	-	Not applicable
DL	-	Large disc
TP	-	Disc pale temporarily
TC	-	Temporal Crescent
ST	-	Super traction
DG	-	Degenerative changes
SM	-	Simple myopia
SMA	-	Simple myopic astigmatism
CMA	-	Compound myopic astigmatism
PM	-	Pathological myopia
EM	-	Emmetropia
Dist	-	Distant vision
Std	-	Standard
SES	-	Socio – economic status
Sl. No.	-	Serial number
RE	-	Right Eye
LE	-	Left Eye
PH	-	Pin hole
NV	-	Near vision
M1	-	Vertical meridian
M2	-	Horizontal Meridian
SPH	-	Spherical
CYL	-	Cylindrical
Cr - VA	-	Corrected visual acuity
Deg	-	Degrees
WNL	-	Within normal limit

SI No.	Name	Age	Sex	Std	SES	Visual Acuity				Retinoscopy		Correction Given			Cr VA	Ant. Segment	Fundus	Myopia
						Eye	Dist	PH	NV	M1	M2	SPH	CYL	AXIS (deg)				
1	Ajay W	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
2	Ajay M	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
3	Shivraj P	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
4	Shivaji B	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
5	M Ayuf Hyder	7	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
6	Kayas J	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
7	Alok B	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
8	Rohi K	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
9	Aman B	7	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
10	Ganesh A	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
11	Shrinivas P	9	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
12	Rahul N R	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
13	Salim M	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
14	Ashok P	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
15	Kallappa S	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
16	Kanaiya D	8	M	2	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
17	Basavraj N	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
18	Tanveer J	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
19	Praveen K	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
20	Abdul A	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
21	Jeevani D	7	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

22	Veeresh B	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
23	Arjun V	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
24	Sujal B	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
25	Yallappa S	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
26	Pravven G	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
27	Akash B	7	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
28	Siddharth M	7	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
29	Kiran Y	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
30	Altaf R	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
31	Swayal S	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
32	Pratham B	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
33	Amit J	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
34	Sadeeq G	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
35	Krishna K	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
36	Darshan P	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
37	Ismail S	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
38	Mutturaj C	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
39	Raghvendra S	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
40	Muttumali M	9	M	3	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.25	+1.25	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.25	+1.25	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
41	Prashant R	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
42	Lakshman V	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

43	Mohin T	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
44	Umesh S	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
45	Ganesh S	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
46	Sunil A	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
47	Shreyash N	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
48	Shahil U	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
49	Mustaq K	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
50	Ravi C	9	M	3	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
51	Ayub J	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
52	Naveen G	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
53	Darshan W	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
54	Srinivas M	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
55	Shrikanth K	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
56	Avinash P	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
57	Shekhar T	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
58	Sudeep G	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
59	Siddharth K	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
60	Somnath	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
61	Gulab Singh R	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
62	Parshuram M	12	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
63	Praveen S	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

64	Akshay P	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
65	Sujal R	9	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
66	Chatan L	9	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
67	Rohan R	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.50	P	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	EM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
68	Deepak H	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
69	Krishna B	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
70	Prem R	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
71	Ismail S	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
72	Naveed R	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
73	Mutthappa S	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
74	Akash A	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
75	Azad K	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
76	Nikhil R	11	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
77	Lakhan M	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
78	Raju B	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
79	Amar D	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
80	Mahesh B	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
81	Shahi A	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
82	Vivekananda M	11	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
83	Sachin S	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
84	Lakshmikanth B	11	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

85	Basavraj A	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
86	Praveen s	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
87	Iranna R	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
88	Maibub C	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
89	Amarnath S	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
90	Shabir J	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
91	Mallinath A	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
92	Abhishek	10	M	5	III	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
93	Shrishail H	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
94	Asfaq J	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
95	Nikhil M	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
96	Satish P	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
97	Sachin M	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
98	Girish I	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
99	Sunil B	12	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
100	Akash P	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
101	Vinayak B	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
102	Bhimsingh R	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
103	Vishal B	10	M	5	III	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
104	Bharath N	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
105	Sanganna M	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

106	Altaf K	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
107	Ajeem S	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
108	Mallikarjun K	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
109	Sohail B	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
110	Samir K	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
111	Hanumanth S	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
112	Jagdish S	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
113	Saiprasad B	10	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
114	Tushar S	12	M	6	III	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
115	Pratham R	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
116	Prashant C	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
117	Abhishek R	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
118	Rohit R	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
119	Yallappa C	13	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
120	Abhishek R	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
121	Prabhuling R	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
122	Bhagwant R	13	M	6	III	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.25	+0.75	-0.25	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
123	Avinash M	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
124	Asif S	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
125	Javed I	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
126	Ismail H	13	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

127	Akbar M	13	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
128	Ajay A	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
129	Shrinivas B	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
130	Vijay A	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
131	Yakub S	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
132	Arun U	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
133	Arshad M	13	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
134	Sagar G	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
135	Kumar	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
136	Samarth	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
137	Dayanand	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
138	Yogesh	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
139	Ruthik	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
140	M.Rihan	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
141	Vishwanath	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
142	Manjunath	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
143	Kiran	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
144	Pavan	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
145	Varun	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
146	Chetan	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
147	Akash	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

148	Govind	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
149	Parshuram M	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
150	Nagesh	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
151	Shamsunder	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
152	Akash	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
153	Dilraj	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
154	Akash	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
155	Santosh	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
156	Badrinath	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
157	M. Shafiq	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
158	Abhishek	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
159	Datta	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
160	Umar	12	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
161	Shrishail H	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
162	Santosh	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
163	Vishal B	13	M	7	III	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
164	Sunil B	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
165	Kiran	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
166	Sachin	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
167	Mahantesh B	13	M	8	III	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
168	Pranav R	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

169	Gurubasappa	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
170	Abhishek J	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
171	Altaf S	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
172	Kiran R	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
173	Muttappa	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
174	Rohit S	14	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
175	Sangu S	14	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
176	Ganesh M	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
177	Rahil M	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
178	Kiran K	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
179	Aftab B	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
180	Raju Y	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
181	Shrinivas G	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
182	Mallikarjun D	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
183	Prakash A	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
184	Akshay G	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
185	Mahesh P	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
186	Mahesh D	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
187	Santosh D	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
188	Ganesh D	13	M	8	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
189	Akash R	14	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

190	Pooja H	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
191	Shabana	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
192	Jayshree	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
193	Rakshita B	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
194	Pavitra R	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
195	Payal S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
196	Raziya begum	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
						LE	CF 5mt	6/12	N6	-3.25	-3.25	-4.50	NA	NA	6/12	VKC	WNL	SM
197	Saniya M	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
198	Rubina A	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
199	Megha D	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
200	Priya R	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
201	Muskan A	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
202	Vaishnavi S	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
203	Kaveri S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
204	Akshatha S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
205	Bhavani S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
206	Priya C	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
207	Davalbi D	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
208	Aishwarya C	8	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
209	Pallavi S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
210	Gousiya B	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

211	Kaveri B	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
212	Dannamma B	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
213	Savitri S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
214	Muskan R	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
215	Shivlila S	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
216	Shrigauri	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
217	Keerthi M	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
218	Priyanka P	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
219	Pallavi Y	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
220	Savitri M	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
221	Shraddha S	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
222	Khatija L	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
223	Firoza A	7	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
224	Nikita R	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
225	Shruti A	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
226	Meenakshi S	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
227	Sneha A	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
228	Pooja N	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
229	K Pandita	10	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
230	Aishwarya R	10	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
231	Bhavani P	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

232	Madhmati S	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
233	Lakshmi L	10	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
234	Danamma A	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
235	Shobha K	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
236	Shakshi A	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
237	Kumkum P	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
238	Rakshita P	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
239	Danamma M	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
240	Megha Y	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
241	Sireen S	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
242	Aiesha J	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
243	Aiesha M	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
244	Kausarbanu P	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
245	Pooja p	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
246	Daneshwari N	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
247	Jyoti D	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
248	Megha J	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Bitot Spot	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Bitot Spot	WNL	NA
249	Prema M	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
250	Arti R	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
251	Danamma H	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
252	Shivlila M	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

253	Pallavi P	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
254	Akshatha J	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
255	Bhagyashree S	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
256	Shakshi P	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
257	Pavitra H	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
258	Yahoda M	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
259	Deepa N	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
260	Apoorva C	10	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
261	Kajal P	10	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
262	Pooja K	8	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
263	Shila A	12	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
264	Deepali K	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
265	Supriya M	12	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
266	Priyanaka T	11	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
267	Pushpa H	10	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
268	Kaveri A	10	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
269	Rakshitha C	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
270	Sushmita J	11	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
271	Kaveri S	11	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
272	Pavitra K	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
273	Rajeshwari K	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

274	Prema H	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
275	Aishwaraya V	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
276	Aishwarya P	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
277	Uma H	13	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
278	Sweta B	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
279	Aiyesh S	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
280	Samarin K	8	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
281	Najma J	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.25	-0.75	90	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	SMA
282	Saniya J	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
283	Reshma M	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
284	Muskan J	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
285	Reshma s	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
286	Heena kausar S	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
287	Saniya S	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
288	Rasoolbi H	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
289	Salma J	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
290	Apsana J	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
291	Rubina J	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
292	Ruksana J	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
293	Aishwarya H	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
294	Mehek M	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

295	Heena T	8	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
296	Aishwarya H	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
297	Sangeeta Y	10	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
298	Kaushalya S	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
299	Chaitra P	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
300	Anita K	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
301	Zeba	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
302	Sonali S	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
303	Amruta C	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
304	Mangala B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
305	Priyanka B	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
306	Ashwini R	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
307	Yashwini T	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
308	Ambika P	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
309	Dilshad B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
310	Asma M	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
311	Apsana S	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
312	Aiysha M	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
313	Apsara S	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
314	Bibi Fatima	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
315	Pallavi B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

316	Shakina J	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
317	Ruksan Bi	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
318	Simran K	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
319	Kareena U	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
320	Pratiksha S	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
321	Archana B	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
322	Mahek K	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
323	Ashwini K	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
324	Mumtaza B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
325	Muskanabi B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
326	Swati K	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
327	Aishwarya S	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
328	Shilpa M	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
329	Swati D	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
330	Pooja K	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
331	Sonam K	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
332	Manisha P	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
333	Akshatha G	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
334	Rashmi A	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
335	Rajeshwari K	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
336	Anjali G	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

337	Mukti A	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
338	Priya A	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
339	Meenakshi P	11	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
340	Manisha P	11	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
341	Komal S	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
342	Keerthi P	10	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
343	Renuka Y	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
344	Pooja M	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
345	Nirmala S	10	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
346	Rohini R	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
347	Iaimanparveen P	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
348	Kalavati G	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
349	Bhuvneshwari S	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
350	Vaishali M	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
351	Lakshmi P	10	G	6	IV	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.75	-2.75	-4.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.75	-2.75	-4.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
352	Prema S	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
353	Swapna D	11	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
354	Vaishnavi P	10	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
355	Kaveri P	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
356	Bharthi E	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
357	Deepa B	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

358	Savitri B	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
359	Bhagyashri M	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
360	Aishwarya B	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
361	Reshma M	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
362	Jabeena E	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
363	Alfia A	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
364	Haseena M	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
365	Chaitra L	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.75	-1.00	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.75	-1.00	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
366	Pooja U	11	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
367	Danamma S	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
368	Shilpa M	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
369	Salma K	14	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
370	Surekha	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
371	Swapna M	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
372	Rani M	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
373	Sana M	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
374	Bibi Aisha	14	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
375	Sadiya P	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
376	Nilofar P	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
377	Muskan J	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
378	Rani B K	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

379	Megha S	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
380	Priyanka B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
381	Vaishnavi S	11	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
382	Apoorva H	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
383	Bhavani K	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
384	Deepa M	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
385	Malashri R	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
386	Bhavani K	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
387	Yamuna P	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
388	Asha B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
389	Simran S	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
390	Nasreena T	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
391	Sweta C	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
392	Aliya	11	G	7	IV	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	NA	NA	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis, SPK	WNL	SM
393	Vijaylakshmi S	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
394	Lata A	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
395	Pallavi D	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
396	Bhavani C	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
397	Surekha	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
398	Salma K	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
399	Sweta B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

400	Vidya	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
401	Anita S	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
402	Navita S	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
403	Nigamma S	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
404	Daneshwari S	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
405	Khuresha B	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
406	Meghrani I	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
407	Bhuvneshwari B	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
408	Aishwarya H	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
409	Sanjota S	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
410	Sharanakka	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
411	Muskan S	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
412	Soundra I	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
413	Sangeeta B	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
414	Priyanka A	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
415	Aishwarya B. B	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
416	Mayuri L	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
417	Bhagirathi B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
418	Vaishnavi A	12	G	7	III	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.50	+0.75	0.00	-0.75	160	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.50	+0.75	0.00	-0.75	160	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
419	Afrin H	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
420	Poornima C	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

421	Vidya B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
422	Lakshmi M	14	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
423	Bhuvaneshwari S B	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
424	Mallan M	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
425	Shruti M	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
426	Bhavani B	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
427	Deepa N	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
428	Sameer	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
429	Arthi R	7	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
430	Praveen S	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
431	Shradhha	7	G	2	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
432	Pavan P	7	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
433	Mahantesh K	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
434	Sameer G	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
435	Gayatri M	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
436	Shrushti	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
437	Sneha S	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
438	Salma G	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
439	Azeem B	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
440	Preeti	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
441	Sangeeta G	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

442	Sagar H	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
443	Pramod	8	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
444	Basavraj T	9	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
445	Ajay C	9	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
446	Akshtha B	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
447	Praveen C	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
448	Aneeta J	11	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
449	Praveen S	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
450	Priyanka B	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
451	Manodh B	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
452	Mallangouda B	10	M	5	III	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	-0.25	-0.25	-1.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	-0.25	-0.25	-1.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
453	Saraswati N	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
454	Geeta H	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
455	Arun R	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
456	Naayem B	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
457	Noorahmed	13	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
458	Rahul B	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
459	Akshay F	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
460	Bhabusa K	10	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
461	Siakumar J	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
462	Ramu G	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

463	Nisarga	11	M	6	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
464	Priya P	11	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
465	Banaduri G	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
466	Meenakshi J	11	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
467	Reshma B	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
468	Shreekanth G	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
469	Shilpa G	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
470	Supriya P	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
471	Mithun S	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
472	Bhimsing G	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
473	Rahul K	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
474	Srimanth G	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
475	Rohit B	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
476	Ibrahim S	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
477	Maruti G	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
478	Malahari G	12	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
479	Pallavi N	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
480	Sweta B	11	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
481	Pallavi J	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
482	Suhasini Y	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
483	Sujatha S	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

484	Pooja P	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
485	Lakshmi A	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
486	Durga M	12	G	7	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.50	0.00	-0.50	170	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.50	0.00	-0.50	170	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
487	Nishkath S	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
488	Akshatha S	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
489	Renuka K	12	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
490	Rekha B	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
491	Shashikanth D	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
492	Paigamber F	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
493	Shantkumar P	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
494	Kavita	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
495	Aishwarya K	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
496	Komal M	13	G	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
497	Swapna M	13	G	8	III	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-1.25	-2.50	-0.50	180	6/6	VKC	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-1.25	-2.50	-0.50	165	6/6	VKC	WNL	CMA
498	Anita R	13	G	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
499	Savita T	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
500	Mustafa J	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
501	Shridevi G	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
502	Reshma C	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
503	Renuka B	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
504	Pooja C	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

505	Radhika K	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
506	Shilpa B	13	G	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
507	Vikkii B	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
508	Jagdish L	13	M	8	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
509	Hanumanth	13	M	8	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
510	Akash T	14	M	9	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
511	Arti H	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
512	Ismail S	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
513	Mahesh H	14	M	9	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
514	Gangamma K	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
515	Ganpati K	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
516	Lakshmi A	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
517	Lakshmi	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
518	Misba Y	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
519	M Vashim M	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
520	Ninganna S	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
521	Pavan H	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
522	Pooja	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
523	Rekha R	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
524	Renuka N	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
525	Renuka G	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA

526	Savita	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
527	Shahid P	14	M	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
528	Shankamma A	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
529	Sneha B	14	G	9	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
530	Varsha B	14	G	9	Iii	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
531	M Arshad	15	M	10	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
532	Vijyalakshmi	15	G	10	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
533	Rohit B	15	M	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
534	Ashwini N	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
535	R Megha	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
536	Pundalik T	15	M	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
537	Rubina J	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
538	Savita H	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
539	Shaila G	15	G	10	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
540	Appasab S	15	M	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
541	Sujata T	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
542	Tulsiram B	15	M	10	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
543	Lakshmi D	15	G	10	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.25	+0.75	-0.25	-0.50	100	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
544	Ayappa S	15	M	10	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
545	Vijyalakshmi K	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
546	Asha H	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

547	Sarika B	15	G	10	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
548	Vidyashree B	15	G	10	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
549	Santosh	9	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
550	Sanganna G	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
551	Anika	9	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
552	Ananya	9	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
553	Kavita	8	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
554	Shruti	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
555	Keerti	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
556	Pramod	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
557	Sujay	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
558	Aishwarya	8	G	2	III	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
559	Sahana	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
560	Keerti	8	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
561	Darshan P	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
562	Darshan	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
563	Praveen	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
564	Sunil	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
565	Pramod	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
566	Vinod	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
567	Swaraj	8	M	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

568	Chaitra	8	G	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
569	Deepika	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
570	Nivedita	8	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
571	Saburi	9	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
572	Geeta	9	G	2	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
573	Danamma	10	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
574	Nikita	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
575	Pooja	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
576	Boramma	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
577	Aishwaraya	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
578	Vaishnavi	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
579	Lakshmi	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
580	Nikhita	9	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
581	Rakshitha	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
582	Sushmita	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
583	Pavitra	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
584	Ankita	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
585	Mahananda	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
586	Karthik	10	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
587	Santosh	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
588	Shivanand	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

589	Guru	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
590	Ravi J	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
591	Punith	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
592	Kiran	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
593	Niranjan	8	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
594	Ashwini	8	G	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
595	Vaishali	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
596	Lakshmi	9	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
597	Sangeeta	8	G	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
598	Akash	9	M	3	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
599	Saifan	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
600	Nayan	9	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
601	Abhishek	10	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
602	Guru	8	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
603	Sanjeevani	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
604	Pavitra	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
605	Soumya	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Bitot Spot	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Bitot Spot	WNL	NA
606	Mayuri	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
607	Rohit	10	M	3	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
608	Rahul	10	M	3	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
609	Anusha	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

610	Sanjana	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
611	Saujanya	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
612	Akshatha	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.50	P	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	EM
						LE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.75	-2.75	-4.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
613	Nikhita	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
614	Vishalgouda	9	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
615	Abhishek	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
616	Mallikarjun	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
617	Akshay	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
618	Kiran	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
619	Prem	12	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
620	Lokesh	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
621	Chandrasekhar	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
622	Vijaykumar	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
623	Arjun	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
624	Rakshita	10	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
625	Sangeeta	11	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
626	Lakshmi	9	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
627	Danamma	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
628	Shraddha	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
629	Nikhita	9	G	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
630	Pratibha	11	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

631	Rajeshwari	10	G	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
632	Naveen	10	M	4	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
633	Dhanush	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
634	Prahlad	10	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
635	Mhantesh	12	M	4	IV	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+1.50	0.00	-0.75	160	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+1.50	0.00	-0.75	165	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	SMA
636	Somu	9	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
637	Saikiran	11	M	4	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
638	Aishwarya	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
639	Komal	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
640	Sahasini	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
641	Kavitha	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
642	Shrushti	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
643	Lakshmi	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
644	Shivlila	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-1.50	-1.50	-3.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
645	Bhagyashree	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
646	Amrutha	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
647	Rani	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
648	Ramya	12	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
649	Vidya	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
650	Mahadevi A	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
651	Asha	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

652	Bhagyashree	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
653	Anjana	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
654	Daneshwari	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
655	Nirmitha	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
656	Anjali	10	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
657	Bhagirathi	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
658	Swathi	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
659	Akshatha	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
660	Kavitha	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
661	Baswalgi	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
662	Deelip	11	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
663	Manikanth	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
664	Basavraj	12	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
665	Basavraj	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
666	Praveen	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
667	Vinodh	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
668	Vishal	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
669	Akash	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
670	Prasann	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
671	Sangmesh	10	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
672	Prajwal	11	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

673	Karthik	11	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
674	Sachidanand	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
675	Karan	11	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
676	Nilkanth	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
677	Gautham	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
678	Mallikarjun	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
679	Abhishek	11	M	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
680	Neelambika	11	G	5	IV	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-2.00	-1.50	-3.00	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.50	0.00	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
681	Muttana G	11	M	5	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
682	Priyanka	11	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
683	Shivaji	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
684	Bhimanna	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
685	Anand	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
686	Achal	11	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
687	Vitthal	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
688	Rohit	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
689	Amar	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
690	Rohit	13	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
691	Pranesh	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
692	Ravikumar	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
693	Akash K	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

694	Sudeep	12	M	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
695	Mallikarjun	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
696	Anand	12	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
697	Manjunath	14	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
698	Aishwarya H	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
699	Rahul	13	M	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
700	Gayatri	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
701	Arti	13	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
702	Kalpana	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
703	Mounika	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
704	Vidhya	12	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
705	Akshatha	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
706	Sneha	13	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
707	Pavithra	13	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
708	Bhuvneshwari	13	G	6	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
709	Deekshita P	12	G	6	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
710	Shivani P	15	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
711	Shilpa N	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
712	Sangeeta S	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
713	Preethi	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
714	Sangeeta	15	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

715	Soujanya	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
716	Vidhya R	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
717	Anjana V	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
718	Swathi	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
719	Manjula R	14	G	7	IV	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	70	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	80	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
720	Mitravati	14	G	7	III	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
721	sharabgouda	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
722	Nikhil	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
723	Arun P	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
724	Sachin C	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
725	Susheel K	14	M	7	IV	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
726	Jakappa	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
727	Shivadev P	14	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
728	Mallikarjun	12	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
729	Arun V	13	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
730	Amokshit p	14	M	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
731	Rahul	15	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
732	Rakesh	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
733	Sabhu	13	M	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
734	Soujanya	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
735	Arpita	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

736	Pooja Y	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
737	Soubhagya	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
738	Akshatha	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
739	Shilpa B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
740	Shushma	13	G	7	III	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-1.50	-1.50	-3.00	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	SM
741	Pooja B	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
742	Arpita	14	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
743	Bhagyashree	14	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
744	Lakshmi	12	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
745	Shruti L	13	G	7	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
746	Ashwini	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
747	Sneha	13	G	7	IV	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
748	Harsha P	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
749	Ishwari S	8	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
750	Shrushti H	8	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
751	Uday J	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
752	Tanisha J	8	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
753	Sudarshan	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
754	Shrushti	8	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
755	Sanjan N	8	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
756	Sanath P	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

757	Sanvir C	8	M	2	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
758	Rahul J	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
759	Raksha J	8	G	2	III	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
760	Nanadini A	8	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
761	Karthik A	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
762	Kareena R	8	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
763	Poorvi D	8	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
764	Sujay N	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
765	Ishwar A	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
766	Amogh P	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
767	Bhagat J	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
768	Mallikarjun D	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
769	Sampath H	10	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
770	Pratham A	8	M	2	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.50	+0.75	0.00	-0.75	110	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.50	+0.75	0.00	-0.75	130	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
771	Abhishek N	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
772	Tejashwini L	7	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
773	Perna	8	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
774	Jyoti U	7	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
775	Arpita L	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
776	Basangouda	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
777	Danamma	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

778	Hrishikesh	10	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
779	Keerti R	9	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
780	Kartik	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
781	Esha S	9	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
782	Parvati	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/9	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
783	Nihal	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
784	Pooja	9	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
785	Laxmi B	8	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
786	Shakshi S	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
787	Sahana S	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
788	Rushikesh M	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
789	Praful D	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
790	Moksh	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
791	Shreya P	10	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
792	Shrushti M	9	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
793	Supreet N	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
794	Sondarya A	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
795	Soniya A	10	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
796	Aditi G	10	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
797	Aryan P	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
798	Aditya C	10	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

799	Hrishikesh G	10	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
800	Vashisth M	9	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
801	Amarnath N	10	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
802	Samad	9	M	3	II	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
803	Lingangouda P	9	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
804	Sidhant	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
805	Veeresh C	10	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
806	Pavan T	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
807	Mayuri	9	G	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
808	Suman J	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
809	Jhanvi B	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
810	Sneha J	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
811	Smriti	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
812	Shruti P	9	G	3	I	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
813	spandana	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
814	Sanjana V	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
815	Venkatesh C	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
816	Sarvesh	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
817	Sitaram	10	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
818	Sumit J	10	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
819	Saloni D	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

820	Abhishek	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
821	Nivedita M	10	G	4	I	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.25	-0.75	-2.25	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.25	-0.75	-2.25	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
822	Nachiket D	10	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
823	Varun	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
824	Tohid S	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
825	Khwaja R	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
826	Vishwanath H	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
827	Rohit J	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
828	Prasanna C	9	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
829	Suhask K	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
830	Sujal M	8	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
831	Rohit B	10	M	4	II	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.50	-1.50	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
832	Nikhil P	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
833	Aishwarya P	8	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
834	Neha N	10	G	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
835	Lisha J	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
836	Ankita N	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
837	Vaishnavi A	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
838	Gauri S	9	G	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
839	Aditya A	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
840	Rohit P	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

841	Raheem I	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
842	Aryan H	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
843	Appaji S	10	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
844	Samarth M	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
845	Dhruv P	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
846	Satyadarshan B	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
847	Shreyash M	8	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
848	Sarvesh B	10	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
849	Vishalaxmi N	11	G	5	I	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-1.25	-0.50	-2.00	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/60	6/12	N6	-1.25	-0.50	-2.00	-0.75	170	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
850	Megha	12	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
851	Prachi	11	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
852	Dilshad I	12	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
853	Pankaj B	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
854	Kartik	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
855	Laxmi	11	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
856	Nikhil J	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
857	Juned B	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
858	Vaishnavi P	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
859	Pravalika J	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
860	Sadhana K	11	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
861	Savika B	10	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

862	Bhoomi B	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
863	Sanjana P	10	G	5	III	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
864	Rakshita	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
865	Keerti N	10	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
866	Pratiksha	9	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
867	Poornima K	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
868	Harsha	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
869	Nidhi J	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
870	Raj G	11	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
871	Sarfaraz S	10	M	5	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.25	-0.25	-1.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
872	Shree M	9	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
873	Saurabh B	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
874	Rahul J	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
875	Praveen G	10	M	5	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.25	-1.25	-2.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
876	Bhavesh J	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
877	Vineet H	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
878	Arvind S	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
879	Supreet N	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
880	Anis B	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
881	Mayur P	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
882	Vineet J	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

883	Akshat J	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
884	Vinayak K	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
885	Rahul B	11	M	6	I	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.00	-1.50	-3.00	-0.50	180	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.00	-1.50	-3.00	-0.50	180	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
886	Shashank D	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
887	Pranav K	11	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
888	Sahil R	11	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
889	Shridhar B	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
890	Pragnesh K	11	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
891	Sunil K	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
892	Samarth B	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
893	Rahul P	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
894	Dhanraj H	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
895	Abhishek P	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
896	Sameer K	11	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
897	Harsh O	12	M	6	I	RE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
898	NiREsh S	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
899	Anurag P	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
900	Naina P	10	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
901	Akshatha N	10	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
902	Nikita B	11	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
903	Aishwarya A	12	G	6	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM

904	Aishwarya M	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
905	Soumaya H	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
906	Perna J	12	G	6	I	RE	CF 4mt	6/6	N6	-3.75	-3.75	-5.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	TC	SM
						LE	CF 5mt	6/9	N6	-3.00	-3.00	-4.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	TC	SM
907	Apoorva R	11	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
908	Avantika B	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
909	Nutan U	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
910	Kavya J	11	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
911	Plmina J	11	G	6	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	60	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
912	Drishti O	11	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
913	Pooja P	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
914	Kavya J	11	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
915	Tanishq M	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
916	Shakshi B	11	G	6	I	RE	6/60	6/6	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/60	6/6	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
917	Afzal H	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
918	Raju K	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
919	Sidhhu P	13	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
920	Asif m	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
921	Vijaykumar H	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
922	Praful S	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
923	Abdul K	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
924	Suraj J	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

925	Harsh C	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
926	Omkar S	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
927	Sachin J	14	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
928	Aliraza M	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
929	Shreya J	14	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
930	Sajid J	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
931	Jakappa P	14	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
932	Rakhi C	14	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
933	Priya B	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
934	Sneha B	12	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
935	Pooja C	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
936	Shreya B	13	G	7	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
937	Pooja K	13	G	7	I	RE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-3.75	-3.75	-5.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-3.75	-3.75	-5.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
938	Priya B	11	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
939	Amarnulla M	13	M	7	II	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
940	Suraj R	13	M	7	I	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
						LE	6/60	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
941	Bhavik D	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
942	Shreevatsa M	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
943	Prithvi R	13	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
944	Sushmita M	12	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
945	Anushree A	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

946	Sreya N	13	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
947	Bhagya M	13	G	7	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
948	Sanskriti B	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
949	Anjali R	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
950	Saloni J	11	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
951	Ashwini B	12	G	7	II	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.25	-1.25	-2.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
952	Supriya A	12	G	7	II	RE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-3.50	-3.50	-5.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-3.50	-3.50	-5.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
953	Ayesha A	12	G	7	I	RE	6/60	6/6	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/6	N6	-1.25	-1.25	-2.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
954	Vaishnavi G	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
955	Vishwajit S	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
956	Meet P	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
957	K S Ajay	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
958	Sahil J	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
959	Mukhtar M	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
960	Shivraj B	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
961	Sourabh S	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
962	Mokshit R	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
963	Abhishek S	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
964	Adesh B	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
965	Yogesh B	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
966	Dheeraj O	13	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

967	Manjunath S	14	M	8	II	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.00	+0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
968	Sujay M	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
969	Suraj B	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
970	Prerna B	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
971	Pavitra K	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
972	Smrti V	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
973	Aishwarya M	14	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
974	Ruksar I	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
975	Sonu D	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
976	Satwik S	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
977	Maruti T	14	M	8	II	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
978	Dinkar S	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
979	Rahul L	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
980	Sudhir S	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/9	WNL	WNL	NA
981	Dareppa N	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
982	Pooja A	12	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
983	Poornima R	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
984	Rachana B	12	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
985	Prerna K	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
986	Aishwaraya S	14	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
987	Siddhi V	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

988	Snehlata S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
989	Rani T	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
990	Preeti B	12	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
991	Swapna B	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
992	Kavya S	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
993	Bhavi B	14	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
994	Kashish R	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
995	Soniya M	12	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
996	Raksha O	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
997	Kartik S	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
998	Ashutosh R	12	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
999	Supreet G	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1000	Mahipal A	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1001	Chirag R	12	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1002	Aman D	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1003	Vedant S	13	M	8	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+1.00	+0.50	-0.50	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
1004	Amogh B	13	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1005	Netravati S	14	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1006	Shruti C	13	G	8	I	RE	CF 4mt	6/12	N6	-5.00	-5.00	-6.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	DL,TC,ST	SM
						LE	CF 5mt	6/12	N6	-3.75	-3.75	-5.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	DL,TC	SM
1007	Pooja S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-1.25	-1.25	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1008	Rashmi L	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1009	Poornima S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/36	6/6	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/6	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1010	Supraja M	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1011	Tejashwini S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1012	Divya I	14	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1013	Soujanya B	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1014	Sneha S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1015	Adil M	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1016	Harshvardhan S	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1017	Shashikant S	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1018	Shrisant J	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1019	Raghunandan R	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1020	Prajwal P	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1021	Vishal G	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1022	Vinay U	12	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1023	Mallikarjun A	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	NA
1024	Samanulla A	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1025	Anusha S	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1026	Laxmi	15	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1027	Vaibhav O	14	M	9	II	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
1028	Kashibai A	14	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1029	Ashwini G	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1030	Phulwanti S	14	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1031	Lakshmi B	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1032	Riya H	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1033	Pooja S	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1034	Sachin H	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1035	Sachin M	15	M	9	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1036	Somasekhar C	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1037	Shripad A	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1038	Indrajeet S	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1039	Sandesh H	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1040	Vinod S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1041	Avinash S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1042	Nivedita A	14	G	9	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+1.00	-0.50	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+1.00	-0.50	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
1043	Gauri S	14	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1044	Ranjita H	14	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1045	Dhareesh S	14	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1046	Roshan S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1047	Akash B	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1048	Ashish S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1049	Javed S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1050	prasad S	14	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1051	Vishwa R	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1052	Mohamad Z	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1053	Arvind	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1054	Md Arshad	14	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1055	Bhavesh R	13	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1056	Mahesh K	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1057	Sushma B	14	G	9	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1058	Shilpa D	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1059	Pragati P	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1060	Akshatha B	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1061	Praneeta J	14	G	9	I	RE	CF 3mt	6/12	N6	-9.00	-10.00	-10.25	-1.00	90	6/12	WNL	DL,AC,ST,DG	CMA
						LE	6/60	6/6	N6	-2.00	-2.75	-3.25	-0.75	90	6/6	WNL	DL,AC,ST	CMA
1062	Gauri P	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1063	Soujanya C	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1064	Deepa A	15	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1065	Minal D	13	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1066	Muskan O	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1067	Rashmi J	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1068	Brunda B	13	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1069	Saniya J	15	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1070	Sushmita G	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1071	Prajwal K	13	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1072	Ashwin P	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1073	Abhishek J	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1074	Naveen G	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1075	Satish P	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1076	Vijay P	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1077	Varun K	13	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1078	Abhishek K	13	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1079	Prateek K	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1080	Sohail S	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1081	Sourabh J G	14	M	9	I	RE	CF 3mt	6/9	N6	-8.75	-8.75	-10.00	NA	NA	6/9	WNL	DL,TC,ST,DG	SM
						LE	CF 4mt	6/6	N6	-6.00	-6.00	-7.25	NA	NA	6/9	WNL	DL,TC	SM
1082	Rohit J	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1083	Viresh A	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1084	Badal O	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1085	Revansiddaya	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1086	Rishabh J	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1087	Akshay B	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1088	Apoorva P	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1089	Kishan M	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1090	Rohan J	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1091	Vinay I	15	M	10	I	RE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-6.00	-6.75	-7.25	-0.75	90	6/9	WNL	DL,TC	CMA
						LE	CF 3mt	6/9	N6	-8.75	-9.50	-10.00	-0.75	90	6/9	WNL	DL,TC,ST,DG	CMA
1092	Avinash S	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1093	Vishvanath D	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1094	Md Gousepak K	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1095	Sachin H	15	M	10	I	RE	CF 5mt	6/9	N6	-3.50	-3.50	-5.00	NA	NA	6/9	WNL	DL,TC	SM
						LE	CF 5mt	6/9	N6	-3.50	-3.50	-5.00	NA	NA	6/9	WNL	DL,TC	SM
1096	Rakesh P	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1097	Abhishek J	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1098	Hrishikesh G	15	M	10	I	RE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-6.00	-6.75	-7.25	-0.75	90	6/6	WNL	DL,TC,ST	CMA
						LE	CF 4mt	6/9	N6	-6.00	-6.75	-7.25	-0.75	90	6/6	WNL	DL,TC,ST	CMA
1099	Arun N	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1100	Azeem H	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1101	Asok A	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1102	Ritu P	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1103	Akash P	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1104	Akshatha B	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1105	Ashwini S	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1106	Sweta H	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1107	Vaishnavi N	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1108	Sarayu D	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1109	Amruta D	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1110	Spoorti P	15	G	10	II	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1111	Vaishnavi R	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1112	Maheshwari H	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1113	Madhura J	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1114	Shrushti B	14	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1115	Sumati ST	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1116	Shivani R	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1117	Rohan C	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1118	Sunil B	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1119	Akshatha B	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1120	Narendra VN	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1121	Arun H	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1122	Sourabh K	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1123	Sidangouda P	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1124	Rahul N	14	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1125	Parikshit A	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1126	Shivbasavrajendra P	14	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1127	Shobhit M	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1128	Akshay B	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1129	Manjunat T	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1130	Shivkumar H	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1131	Ramannagouda B	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1132	Kalpesh j	15	M	10	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	SPK	WNL	CMA
1133	Shripad J	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1134	Naresh B	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1135	Santosh P	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1136	Malleshappa P	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1137	Aishwarya J	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1138	Aishwarya T	15	G	10	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.25	+0.75	-0.25	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
1139	Swaruparani N	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1140	Saifali J	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1141	Shambhavi C	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1142	Varsha H	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1143	Shalini J	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1144	Priyanka C	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1145	Pragnya M	15	G	10	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1146	Laxmi M	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1147	Priya P	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1148	Poorva N	15	G	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1149	Deepa K	15	G	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1150	Shweta M	15	G	10	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	SMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.00	0.00	-0.50	90	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	SMA
1151	Prasanna P	15	M	10	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1152	Kiran P	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1153	Kiran N	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1154	Zubair B	15	M	10	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1155	Ananaya R	7	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1156	Bhagyashree H	7	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1157	Karishma S	7	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1158	Keerti R	7	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1159	Priya C	7	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1160	Reshma R	7	G	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1161	Sharaddha A	8	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1162	Shreya K	7	G	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1163	Abhishek C	7	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1164	Aditya S	7	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1165	Aman	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1166	Anup S	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	Conj. Xerosis	WNL	NA
1167	Ashish C	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1168	Gurulingayya H	8	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1169	Manavkumar	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1170	Nagaraj D	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1171	Niranjan P	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1172	Omkar S	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1173	Piyush J	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1174	Prajwal M	8	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1175	Praveen E	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1176	Rajshekhar A	7	M	2	I	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM

1177	Rakshit C	7	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1178	Rohit L	7	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1179	Roshan L	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1180	Rudragouda B	7	M	2	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1181	Vaibhav K	7	M	2	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1182	Akshatha R	8	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1183	Akshata H	8	G	3	II	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
						RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	VKC	WNL	SM
1184	Divya R	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1185	Laitha C	9	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1186	Nikita M	8	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1187	Ritu R	8	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1188	Shilpa J	9	G	3	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.25	-0.25	-1.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1189	Supriya H	8	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1190	Yashashwini D	8	G	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1191	Abhishek P	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1192	Abhishek R	10	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1193	Akash R	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1194	Chandrashekhar S B	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1195	Charanjeet N H	8	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.50	P	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	EM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1196	Gurugouda B	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1197	Kartik B	9	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1198	Manjunath K	8	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1199	Mutthuraj P	10	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1200	Prajwal K	9	M	3	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1201	Pramod C	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1202	Pranav R	9	M	3	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1203	Apparna J	9	G	4	I	RE	6/60	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.75	-3.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/9	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1204	Bhavysawati R	9	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1205	Daneshwari M	9	G	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1206	Parvati K	10	G	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1207	Pradhanya B	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1208	Priyanka N	10	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1209	Rinkukumar	9	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1210	Shreya P	9	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1211	Shrushti P	9	G	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1212	Swapna C	9	G	4	I	RE	6/36	6/6	N6	-1.50	-1.50	-3.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.75	-0.75	-2.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1213	Adarsh K	11	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1214	Adarsh P	11	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1215	Anup B	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1216	Bharath K	11	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1217	Md Ali S	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1218	Mohan C	9	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1219	Nitin N	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1220	Rakesh C	11	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1221	Rohan R	12	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1222	Rohit R	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1223	Sampathkumar	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1224	Shivputra B	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1225	Shivraj P	10	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1226	Sudarsha B	10	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1227	Sujeet S	9	M	4	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1228	Vivek P	10	M	4	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1229	Aishwarya j	11	G	5	I	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1230	Ankita R	12	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1231	Archana G	11	G	5	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.25	+0.75	-0.25	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+1.25	+0.75	-0.25	-0.50	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
1232	Neelamma R.S	11	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1233	Ranjeeta D	11	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1234	Shivani N	10	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1235	Sounalya .RS	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1236	Tejaswini SD	11	G	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1237	Vaishnavi R	10	G	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1238	Vaishnavi W	10	G	5	I	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.00	-1.00	-2.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1239	Abhijeet R H	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1240	Akshay D	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1241	Arvind C	11	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1242	Ashish J	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1243	Karthik .N	10	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1244	Pawan N	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1245	Prajwal B	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1246	Rahul R	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1247	Siddu S	12	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1248	Sumit A	12	M	5	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1249	Sunil R	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1250	Tanveer B	11	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1251	Uday K	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1252	Yallaling W	10	M	5	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1253	Mallikarjun Y	13	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1254	Shiv R	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1255	Samarth B	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1256	Kartik P	13	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1257	Kuldeep S	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1258	Sreyash P	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1259	Rachaiyya H	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1260	Sunil R	12	M	6	II	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	+0.75	0.00	-0.75	-0.75	90	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.50	P	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	EM

1261	Saquib C	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1262	Saikumar B	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1263	Arun B	13	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1264	Venkatesh M	11	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1265	Vaishnavi	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1266	Anjali R	12	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1267	Shweta C	12	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1268	Asifa M	12	G	6	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	0.00	0.00	-1.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1269	Chandrika	12	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1270	Deepa R	11	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1271	Vinay N	12	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1272	Karan	13	M	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1273	Ramesh K	12	M	6	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+1.00	-0.50	-0.50	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/24	6/9	N6	0.00	+0.75	-0.75	-0.75	180	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
1274	Guriraj P	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1275	Manoj K	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1276	Afsan M	12	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1277	Rakesh R	13	M	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1278	Sonali K	12	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1279	Laila S	11	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1280	Sushma C	13	G	6	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1281	Nandini C	12	G	6	I	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.25	-0.25	-1.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM

1282	Ashwini D	12	G	6	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1283	Pallavi P	13	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1284	Deepa G	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1285	Priya H	13	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1286	Vidya P	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1287	Archana B	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1288	Pavitra D	13	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1289	Rashmi D	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1290	Laxmi H	12	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1291	Ashwini R	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1292	Megha R	12	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1293	Pallavi H	11	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1294	Tejashwini S	11	G	7	I	RE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+1.25	-0.25	-0.50	170	6/6	WNL	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.50	0.00	-0.50	165	6/6	WNL	WNL	SMA
1295	Pramila S	12	G	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1296	Vikas	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1297	Mahesh R	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1298	Pradeep	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1299	Ankit C	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1300	Sagar K	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1301	Darshit	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1302	Rahul D	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1303	Rahul C	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1304	Gururaj T	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1305	Amir	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1306	Sujit H	12	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1307	Shubham G	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1308	Rahul R	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1309	Vishwanath A	14	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1310	Sahebgouda P	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1311	Aditya J	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1312	Vinay	13	M	7	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1313	Balaji P	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1314	Sagar I	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1315	Krishna S	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1316	Sachin B	13	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1317	Ishwar C	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	+1.50	+1.50	P	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	EM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.50	+0.50	-1.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1318	Aetesham S	12	M	7	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1319	Abhishek H	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1320	Akhilesh	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1321	Jitendra B	13	M	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1322	Sahitya C	13	G	7	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1323	Shilpa S	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1324	Geetagauri B	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1325	Swapana B	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1326	Soumya M	13	G	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1327	Shruti H	13	G	8	I	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.00	-2.50	-0.75	180	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	CMA
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-1.75	-1.00	-2.50	-0.75	180	6/6	Blephritis	WNL	CMA
1328	Shruti P	13	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1329	Sahana H	12	G	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1330	Sanket B	14	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1331	Nishant P	13	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1332	Samarth A	13	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1333	Samarth P	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1334	Sandeep C	15	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1335	Anand C	13	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1336	Mukesh C	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1337	Muttu B	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1338	Abhishek S	15	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1339	Manjunath L	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1340	Arvind B	15	M	8	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1341	Kamlesh G	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1342	Basavaraj S	13	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1343	Shankar P	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1344	Pandurang H	14	M	8	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1345	Padma S	15	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1346	Neha P	15	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1347	Priyanka R	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1348	Soumya T	15	G	9	I	RE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/18	6/6	N6	+0.25	+0.25	-1.25	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1349	Shashikanth K	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1350	Pooja B	15	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1351	Nameera I	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1352	Varsharani D	14	G	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1353	Vidyashree G	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1354	Sushma H	14	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1355	Pooja D	15	G	9	I	RE	6/9	6/6	N6	+1.00	+1.00	-0.50	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/12	6/6	N6	+0.75	+0.75	-0.75	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1356	Akshatha J	15	G	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1357	Jeevan B	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1358	Akash P	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1359	Sandeep L	14	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1360	Sandeep B	14	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1361	Rohit C	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1362	Rahul B	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1363	Rakesh S	14	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1364	Viresh Nibal	15	M	9	II	RE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
						LE	6/24	6/6	N6	-0.50	-0.50	-2.00	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	SM
1365	Sachin C	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA

1366	Samarth D	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1367	Chetn P	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1368	Chetan R	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1369	Shekhar R	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1370	Amrut B	15	M	9	II	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1371	Sukhdev	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1372	Chetan P	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
1373	Prashant T	15	M	9	II	RE	6/36	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.50	NA	NA	6/6	SPK	WNL	SM
						LE	6/36	6/9	N6	-2.00	-2.00	-3.50	NA	NA	6/6	SPK	WNL	SM
1374	Akash T	15	M	9	I	RE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA
						LE	6/6	6/6	N6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6/6	WNL	WNL	NA